

AMERICAN POLITICAL SCIENCE ASSOCIATION

MENA POLITICS

Newsletter of the Middle East and North Africa Politics Section of APSA

VOL. 8 ISSUE 2, FALL 2025

ISSN: 2996-4911

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Letter From the Editors

Greetings,

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We are pleased to present the Fall 2025 issue of *MENA Politics*, featuring a timely and thought-provoking collection of essays and discussions that reflect the turbulent political environment in which we find ourselves.

This issue opens with two lead essays. First, Laurie Brand offers an authoritative and boldly written assessment of the current state of academic freedom in the US. Her essay is both descriptive – in documenting an onslaught of repression under the Trump administration and how it compares and relates to authoritarianism in the MENA region – and prescriptive – in its forceful calls for scholars, particularly those who are least professionally or personally vulnerable, to demand respect for academic freedom, to refuse to “obey in advance,” and to fulfill our “duty to continue doing what we do,” insisting upon control over our teaching, our speech, and our scholarly analysis. Second, Khalid Medani provides an invaluable, comprehensive primer on the ongoing conflict in Sudan. His essay situates the current war within the broader historical and political economy of the country, highlighting the legacy of authoritarian governance, including parallel military forces, the formal and illicit economy, long standing historical, social, and political divisions, the role of external actors,

and other factors. Medani presents an empirically rich analysis that touches upon important themes relevant to MENA political science.

Next, our readers will find a timely and informative symposium on Syria, a country undergoing profound transformation following the fall of the Asad regime. The symposium’s guest editors are Rana Khoury, outgoing member of our editorial board, and Sefa Secen, and they have assembled a fresh set of contributors, a number of whom are Syrian or Syrian-American, to offer their insightful perspectives on the challenges and possibilities of rebuilding governance and legitimacy in a post-Asad Syria.

Finally, we include a roundtable discussion on the current state of funding and, more generally, knowledge production in MENA social science. Lisa Anderson, Sofia Fenner, Ellen Lust, Jamil Moawad, and Salma Mousa join Diana Greenwald to reflect on the macro level funding landscape today and to share some of their own experiences in securing support for their research. Contributors to the roundtable offer strategies for sustaining scholarly engagement and collaboration under conditions that are increasingly con-

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Letter from the Editors (continued)

strained by developments in both the US and the region.

The publication of the fall issue also marks a transition in our editorial board leadership. We are delighted to welcome two new members to our editorial board – Carolyn Barnett and Salih Yasun – whose biographies can be found below. Their expertise will enrich our editorial vision and strengthen our commitment to fostering rigorous and inclusive scholarship. We are indebted to Bassel Sal-loukh and Rana Khoury for their three years of service on the board.

This season also brings with it a transition in our section's leadership. We extend our deep gratitude to Curtis Ryan, our outgoing section chair, for his tireless efforts and unwavering advocacy on behalf of our colleagues. At the same time, we extend an enthusiastic welcome to Marwa Shalaby, the newly elected section chair, who will undoubtedly bring fresh ideas to motivate our continued, collective work within the section. We also thank outgoing section officers Zahra R. Babar and Lama Mourad, and look forward to working with new and continuing members of the Executive Committee, Sarah El-Kazzaz, Adria Lawrence, Nermin Allam, and Lisel Hintz.

As always, we invite you to reach out with suggestions, feedback, or ideas for future issues. Your engagement is vital to the continued relevance and vibrancy of this newsletter.

- Diana Greenwald, Sebnem Gumuscu, and
Samer Shehata

If you have comments, suggestions, or ideas for future issues and new features
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The Editorial Board's Newest Members

*Carolyn Barnett is an Assistant Professor with a joint appointment in the School of Government and Public Policy and School of Global Studies at the University of Arizona, and a non-resident fellow of the Crown Center for Middle East Studies at Brandeis University. She earned her Ph.D. in Politics from Princeton University. She also holds an M.A. in Islamic Studies and M.Sc. in Middle East Politics from the School of Oriental and African Studies in London, studied in the Center for Arabic Study Abroad program at the American University in Cairo, and earned a B.S.F.S. from Georgetown University in Culture and Politics. Carolyn's research focuses on public opinion, social norms, and political behavior in the Middle East and North Africa, particularly on gender-related issues. Her book project explores why people underestimate public support for gender equality across a range of issues and what the consequences of that pessimism are. The dissertation on which the book builds, *Perceived Norms and the Politics of Women's Rights in Morocco*, was awarded *Best Dissertation* by the APSA MENA Politics Section in 2023 and an *Honorable Mention for Best Fieldwork* by the APSA Democracy & Autocracy Section in 2022. Carolyn's work has appeared in *The Journal of Politics*, *American Journal of Political Science*, *Comparative Political Studies*, *Political Science Research & Methods*, *Politics & Gender*, *PS: Political Science and Politics*, *Democratization*, and *Hawwa*. She is a two-time Fulbright grantee (to Egypt in 2009 and Morocco in 2018), a Marshall Scholar (2010), and before earning her Ph.D. was a research fellow in the Middle East Program at the Center for Strategic and International Studies.*

*Salih Yasun is an Assistant Professor of International Studies and Political Science at the Virginia Military Institute. His research examines the historical and institutional foundations of governance and religion in the Middle East and North Africa, with a particular focus on the enduring legacies of institutions and state-building. His work has been published in journals such as *Democratization*, *Party Politics*, and *Middle East Law and Governance*, among others. He holds a Ph.D. in Political Science and an M.Sc. in Applied Statistics from Indiana University Bloomington. Fluent in Turkish, Ottoman Turkish, and Arabic, Yasun combines archival research with quantitative analysis to investigate how historical institutions shape contemporary political and developmental outcomes. His current project analyzes the long-term consequences of school construction in the Ottoman Empire, situating local educational expansion within broader debates on governance, religion and diversity in the MENA region.*

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News from the APSA MENA Section

Letter from the Section Chair

Dear colleagues,

My term as chair of our section has now come to an end. Thank you for all your support over the last two years and for all the extensive work you've done for our section. I've been honored to serve as chair, and I look forward to supporting our new chair, Marwa Shalaby. In this final report, I want to briefly share with you some news from APSA 2025, as well as the news of our recent elections and awards ceremony.

APSA 2025

I used my role as chair to speak up one last time (at least in my capacity as chair) at the annual APSA meeting for section leaders. I reminded all who were present that I had raised issues of academic freedom the previous year as well, but that now the situation is, of course, even worse. I had said last time that many of the efforts to suppress the voices of people in our section would start with us, but then fan out to be used against others. And unfortunately, I think that is exactly what has happened. I made clear that many of our members now worry about their own ability to speak up, stand up, or show up, without risking their jobs, careers, grants, scholarships, stipends, visa status, or personal safety – and APSA needs to do more. I asked the organization to stand up and be more vocal in support of its own members, as these stresses are now unfortunately familiar to other sections as well, to our profession, and to higher education in general. I also had follow-up discussions on these issues with several APSA officers, who were receptive to these concerns. So I hope that is at least

promising.

Thanks to all who attended our many panels, roundtables, poster sessions, business meeting, and reception at the recent APSA conference in Vancouver, Canada. Special thanks also go to our conference co-chairs, Nermin Allam and Janine Clark, for organizing everything, including 14 panels and a poster session. As usual, our panels were very well-attended and covered a wide range of topics, including migration, urban politics, alliances, foreign policy, methodologies, contentious politics, social movements, gender politics, state-society relations, and public opinion.

Our section also worked with Dana El-Issa and Andrew Stinson to organize a pre-APSA Research Development Group (RDG) for some excellent graduate students and early career scholars from the MENA region. The RDG was a great success, and we hope to replicate that success sometime in the near future with another RDG. Thanks to Dana and Andrew of APSA MENA Workshops and to all of our presenters and discussants, including Bouthaina Ait Ouchaou, Dhouha Jerbi, Ghadir Awad, Mohamed El-Gohari, Zahra Babar, Summer Forester, Lindsay Benstead, and Lisel Hintz.

At our business meeting, we announced the results of our recent elections. Thanks to our nominations committee – Dina Bishara, Tarek Masoud, Yael Zeira – for their hard work organizing our electoral slate. Special thanks to our outgoing officers, Zahra Babar

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News from the APSA MENA Section

Letter from the Section Chair, continued

(treasurer) and Lama Mourad (at-large), for their two years of stellar service for our section, and congratulations to our continuing and newly elected officers.

Here is our new APSA MENA Executive Committee:

Marwa Shalaby, Chair, 2025-27
 Sarah El-Kazzaz, Vice Chair, 2024-26
 Adria Lawrence, Treasurer, 2025-27
 Nermin Allam, At-Large Member, 2024-26
 Lisel Hintz, At-Large Member, 2025-27

At the business meeting, we also presented quite a few awards for scholarly excellence. I am providing the full list of winners and their works, with thanks to each of the awards committees, as they are also noted below.

APSA MENA AWARD WINNERS

Best Book Award:

Winner, Best First Book: Diana Greenwald, *Mayors in the Middle: Indirect Rule and Local Government in Occupied Palestine* (Columbia University Press, 2024).

Winner, Best Book by a Senior Scholar: Günes Murat Tezcür, *Liminal Minorities: Religious Difference and Mass Violence in Muslim Societies* (Cornell University Press, 2024).

Honorable Mention: Rachel Brown, *Unsettled Labors: Migrant Care Work in Palestine/Israel* (Duke University Press, 2024).

Committee: Jillian Schwedler (Chair, Hunter

College, CUNY), Sharan Grewal (American University), Youssef EL-Chazli (Université Paris).

Best Article Award:

Winner: Fiona Adamson (2024), "The Political Geography of Globalized Civil Wars: Networked Actors and Multi-Scalar Strategies in the Kurdish Conflict Assemblage". *International Studies Quarterly*, vol. 68, no. 1, pp. 1-12

Honorable Mention: Neil Ketchley, Ferdinand Eibl & Jeroen Gunning (2024), "Anti-austerity riots in late developing states: Evidence from the 1977 Egyptian Bread Intifada". *Journal of Peace Research*, vol. 61, no. 6, pp. 952-966.

Honorable Mention: Christopher Barrie, Killian Clarke & Neil Ketchley (2024), "Burnings, Beatings, and Bombings: Disaggregating Anti-Christian Violence in Egypt, 2013–2018". *Perspectives on Politics*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 481-500.

Committee: Pete Moore (Chair, Case Western Reserve University), Dana El Kurd (University of Richmond), Morten Valbjørn (Aarhus University).

Best APSA Paper:

Winner: Berfin Baydar and Asli Cansunar, "Homogenizing High Street: Economic Cleansing of Minority Elites through Fiscal Discrimination."

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News from the APSA MENA Section

Letter from the Section Chair, continued

Honorable Mention: Motasem Abuzaid and Kevin Mazur, "Nurturing Revolution: The Role of Social Networks and the Built Environment in the 2011 Syrian Uprising."

Committee: Neil Ketchley (Chair, University of Oxford), Summer Forester (Carleton College), Elizabeth Parker-Magyar (Yale University).

Best Dissertation:

Winner: Elizabeth K. Parker-Magyar, *Workplace Networks and Autonomous Organizations in Contemporary Jordan* (Ph.D., MIT).

Honorable Mention: Rosa Burç, *Building a Society: Kurdish Transformative Mobilization in Times of Violence* (Ph.D., Scuola Normale Superiore).

Honorable Mention: Waleed K. Salem, *Seeing Like a Court: Judicial Agency in Autocratic Regimes and Transition Politics: The Case of Egypt* (Ph.D., University of Washington).

Committee: Wendy Pearlman (Chair, Northwestern University), Jasmine Gani (London School of Economics and Political Science), Lisel Hintz (Johns Hopkins University, SAIS).

Please join me in congratulating the winners of our elections and our section awards, and in thanking all of our members listed above for their extensive service on the executive committee and the awards committees. I look forward to our section's continued work with the REMENA project, with APSA MENA

Workshops, and with the Arab Political Science Network, as well as other key organizations in our field.

Thank you. And best wishes to you all as we all continue to navigate the increasingly difficult challenges to our profession and to the region that we love.

With respect and gratitude,

Curtis Ryan
APSA MENA Section Chair

News from the APSA MENA Program

The American Political Science Association's [MENA Program](#) is a multi-year effort to support political science research and networking among early-career scholars across the Middle East and North Africa. Through a series of workshops, departmental collaborations, research grants, and other opportunities, the program extends APSA's engagement with the international political science community and strengthens research networks linking American scholars with colleagues overseas. The goal of APSA's MENA Workshops, generously funded by Carnegie Corporation of New York through 2025, is to enhance the capacities and resources of political scientists in the Arab MENA region, while also providing a forum for supporting their ongoing research.

In August 2025, APSA organized a 4-day workshop in Amman, Jordan, titled "Addressing Decolonization and Extractivism in Academic Research in the MENA Region." Led by Drs. Rola El-Husseini (Lund University), Sarah Anne Rennick (Arab Reform Initiative), Nadine Sika (American University in Cairo), and Saloua Zerhouni (Mohammed V University), the program convened 25 PhD candidates and early-career scholars to discuss the pervasive issue of extractivism in academia within the MENA region, where the exploitation of knowledge and other intellectual resources from marginalized communities and local research partners remains prevalent. Through thematic discussions and group exercises, participants engaged with critical issues in decolonial research, including intellectual extractivism, research ethics, positionality, and knowledge production. The workshop marked the third methods training following the launch of the [MENA Methods Program Initiative](#) in 2023.

At the September 2025 APSA Annual Meeting in Vancouver, APSA partnered with the MENA Politics Section to host a Research Development Group (RDG) for four early-career MENA scholars. Selected scholars took part in the full-day seminar on Wednesday, September 10, where they discussed and received critical feedback on article-length manuscripts in progress. Papers were circulated in advance to allow time for thorough

reading, with two senior scholars assigned as discussants for each. Drs. Curtis R. Ryan (Appalachian State University), Zahra Babar (Georgetown University), Summer Forester (Carleton College), Lindsay J. Benstead (Portland State University), and Lisel Hintz (Johns Hopkins University) served as the seminar facilitators and discussants. In addition to focused discussions on each paper, the seminar provided tips on academic writing and advice for publishing in peer-reviewed journals and other professional development topics. The RDG provides participants with the opportunity to advance their research manuscripts for publication, engage in the annual meeting, and build scholarly networks with colleagues.

As part of its ongoing partnership with the [Institute for Qualitative and Multi-Method Research](#) (IQMR) at Syracuse University and the [Inter-University Consortium for Political and Social Research](#) (ICPSR) at the University of Michigan, APSA sponsored six MENA-based scholars from Egypt, Lebanon, and Morocco to attend the 2025 Summer Programs in the US. The partnerships aim to expand support for MENA-based scholars by providing advanced methodology training at premier U.S. institutions.

Looking ahead, APSA will host another 4-day MENA Methods training program on Engag-

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News from the APSA MENA Program (continued)

ed Research in the Middle East and North Africa at the Doha Institute for Graduate Studies in January 2026. The workshop will be led by Drs. Lara Khattab (Doha Institute), Stacey Philbrick Yadav (Hobart and William Smith), Sarah E. Parkinson (Johns Hopkins University), and Ammar Shamaileh (Doha Institute). Together with selected workshop fellows, co-leaders will focus on enhancing social scientific interest in participatory and engaged scholarship in the MENA region.

The MENA Program continues to support graduate students and early-career scholars through virtual mentoring and professional development opportunities. Earlier this summer, we paired ten graduate students with advanced-career scholars for one-on-one mentorship on their research projects through the [MENA Mentorship Initiative](#). A call for applications for the winter MENA Mentoring cycle will be announced later this fall.

For more information about the MENA Program should visit the project website at <http://web.apsanet.org/mena/> or e-mail menaworkshop@apsanet.org.

APSA MENA Project Team
American Political Science Association

News from the Arab Political Science Network

The Arab Political Science Network is a collaborative scholarly initiative that seeks to support Arab political scientists.

Greetings to all!

Our update to the community of political and social science in the Middle East and North Africa comes at a critical time, marking over two years of immense killing, destruction, and displacement across several wars and conflicts in the region. We hope the ceasefire in Gaza that went into effect on October 10 will last for the foreseeable future until a Palestinian State is fully established and recognized.

The commitment of the Arab Political Science Network ([APSN](#)) remains to support students, educators, researchers, and scholars in the region, who are more than ever in need of solidarity and a community. As such, we would like to remind all our colleagues of the digital resources available on our website and on [YouTube](#), particularly the research methods videos that are subtitled in Arabic (make sure to click the CC button if Arabic isn't automatically on). These playlists can be useful for both students and faculty, and include engaging discussions on [Multimethod Research](#), [Archives](#), [Interviews](#), [Text Analysis](#), and [Surveys](#).

After a successful webinar series and workshop focusing on [Politics and War in MENA](#), we launched another series in collaboration with the Arab Reform Initiative ([ARI](#)) focusing on [Syria's Transition](#). The first three sessions looked at post-war paths to stability, political institutions and sectarianism, and domestic political economy. Our upcoming session will focus on *Transitional Justice in Post-War Dynamics* and what the new

Syrian authorities are doing and can do based on lessons from other experiences. Please check our newsletter and social media accounts for an announcement soon.

Last month, APSN participated in the [APSA Annual Meeting](#) in Vancouver, Canada. The roundtable participants looked at how wars influence state sovereignty, economic devastation, and geopolitical dynamics in the MENA region, and what the broader consequences of conflict are on everyday life, gender roles, and transitional justice. Building on that and in collaboration with the Global Academy of the [Middle East Studies Association](#), APSN will organize a roundtable with scholars from the region at the MESA conference in November in Washington, DC. More information will be shared soon, and please join us if you are attending the conference.

We would like to remind you of our specialized two bi-weekly newsletters, [ad-Dal](#) that recommends new non-fiction / social science Arabic and English books, and [az-Zad](#) that provides bilingual abstracts for social science academic journals. These newsletters complement the Arabic book review portal [al-Salon](#) that publishes Arab reviews for non-fiction books about the MENA region and beyond. We welcome any suggestions or possible contributions by writing to info@al-salon.com. Finally, we invite you all to follow us on social media, especially our APSN new [Instagram](#) account, to receive the latest information and opportunities.

Best to all!

Ahmed Morsy (on behalf of the APSN team)

Confronting Authoritarianism at Home and Abroad: Academic Freedom in the Shadow of Genocide

Laurie A. Brand

Laurie A. Brand is Professor Emerita of Political Science & International Relations and Middle East Studies at the University of Southern California, Los Angeles. She has chaired the Middle East Studies Association's Committee on Academic Freedom since 2006.

"...if you can't draw the line at genocide, you probably can't draw the line at democracy." (Coates,¹ 2025)

How are we who have studied, researched, and lived in various parts of the MENA region, and who now find our profession, our universities, our colleagues, our students, and perhaps ourselves under attack by the Trump administration, to understand what is happening? While Coates' charge above was not directed at universities, the link he draws between protesting genocide and defending democracy is central to any discussion of academic freedom in the US today. We are involved in a struggle against anti-democratic forces that seek not only to silence the many voices from both inside and outside universities protesting the genocide in Gaza, but also, simultaneously, to impose a broad authoritarian project of white Christian nationalism on the United States (Heritage Foundation 2023). Making sense of this moment is impossible without a recognition of how these two goals are inextricably linked.

¹ The remarks were made in reference to the Democratic party's support for, or failure to recognize, the genocide.

Setting the Stage

For members of our community of scholars who come from authoritarian states, the current script must feel dreadfully familiar. Many of the rest of us, however, having learned what it is like to live under authoritarian regimes as part of our research on the region, with all that means for the protection of sources, colleagues, data, and the circumscribing of some of the most basic elements of academic freedom, are only now being introduced to what it means to experience state repression at home. The fascist policies (Stanley 2018) of this new administration affect how we live our professional lives not only as teachers and scholars, but also as moral citizens; today's threats are both qualitatively different and worse than threats that have arisen under any previous administration (Schrecker 2025).

As political scientists we should be pondering the forces – economic, political, and social – that lead a democracy with a particularly strong tradition of free speech to turn with such destructive vengeance against the cen-

ters of research and knowledge production that have been foundational to its past political, economic, and military strength. The United States today is often described as experiencing “democratic backsliding” or creeping fascism. Yet, given the extensive territorial, political, and economic reach of the US, we should perhaps instead characterize the current period as one of imperial rot, in which whole groups of people – non-white communities, refugees, migrants, and the homeless here, as well as entire populations in the Global South – are deemed disposable (Fraser 2022). The US empire, increasingly hollowed out internally by rising income inequality, outrageous outlays for illegal interventions abroad, and increasingly militarized policing at home, is trampling the rule of law and purging scientific and technocratic expertise. Championing this destruction is the most incompetent, kleptocratic, and unapologetically vicious leadership in our history, intent upon policies that, far from making America great, are in fact hastening institutional collapse and corrosion from within.²

Academic Freedom and Middle East Studies

The defense of universities as centers of critical inquiry has long been a concern of the scholarly community in the US. The 1940 American Association of University Professors (AAUP) “Statement of Principles on Academic Freedom and Tenure and its amendments” (AAUP, n.d.) continues to serve as a foundational document on academic freedom. However, given the nature of the US political system, with its Constitution and Bill of Rights, the AAUP statement imagined that the threats to academic freedom would come from *within the universities themselves*. It

did not foresee that the primary threats to academic freedom might someday come directly *from the US government*, the situation in which we find ourselves today (Sarat 2025).

Over the years, the community of MENA region scholars, including both political scientists and those from other disciplines, has periodically been in the crosshairs of actors working to suppress our research and teaching. Most have been non-governmental ones seeking to stifle free speech on the Middle East. Palestine has been the most prominent and contentious issue, although critiques of broader US Middle East policy have also triggered harassment. For example, after 9/11 some of our colleagues were targeted for offering analyses that attempted to place the attacks in historical and political context. In the period that followed, we were treated to legions of spurious charges on Daniel Pipes’ *Campus Watch* website. Somewhat later, the even more insidious – because of its anonymity, and its targeting of not just faculty but also students – *Canary Mission* began its attacks.

While some of these assaults targeted writings and speech that were deemed anti-American, the actual goal was to intimidate and, later, with the advance of internet technology, “dox” scholars and students for any criticism of Israel or support for the Boycott Divestment and Sanctions (BDS) movement. For decades before there was an International Holocaust Remembrance Alliance (IHRA) definition of antisemitism and the subsequent pressures to adopt it (Middle East Studies Association 2021; Stern 2025), the charge of antisemitism for criticizing Israeli policies was threatening precisely because of the historical record of the Holocaust and its resonance in

² Referring solely to the cuts across the US intelligence agencies, former CIA director William Burns termed the purges underway as “great-power suicide” (Burns 2025).

the West. Indeed, the most potentially damning charge against scholars in our field has been that of engaging in antisemitic (often perverted to mean anti-*Israel*), not anti-*American*, speech. Thus, while recent surveys of Middle East Studies scholars have documented self-censorship in the classroom (Lynch and Telhami 2023), faculty have long been careful, even after securing tenure, when it came to writing, teaching, and speaking on Palestine.

The Current Assault

To understand what we are facing today under the Trump administration, it is important to first highlight the confluence of several key factors prior to autumn 2023.

First, anti-Palestinian racism, anti-Arab racism, and Islamophobia have long flourished in the US, on and off college campuses; nevertheless, universities in the US had gradually become the epicenter of Palestine solidarity activism, in particular regarding BDS. The proliferation of chapters of Students for Justice in Palestine and Jewish Voice for Peace is among the most obvious indicators of this development. It was precisely to quash this anti-Zionist activism that a range of actors began to actively lobby to legislate or impose the adoption of the 2016 IHRA definition of antisemitism at the federal (Committee on Academic Freedom 2022), state, and even municipal level, as well as at universities.

Just as important, the congressional inquisitions that pilloried presidents of top universities beginning in fall 2023 (Committee on Academic Freedom 2024) demonstrated an increasing eagerness by the political right to instrumentalize antisemitism – defined primarily as anything pro-Palestinian – as part of their long-standing project to discredit

America's institutions of higher learning as bastions of a liberal elite or “radical left” orthodoxy. For these right-wing officials – many of whom espouse a white Christian nationalist ideology which is antisemitic, but not, importantly, anti-Zionist – the goal has precious little to do with antisemitism, for which there should be zero tolerance. Rather, they seek to silence “radical” academics and the institutions that harbor them because they view them as responsible for teaching critical thinking and promoting opposition to their authoritarian political program.

US foreign policy also helped bring us to the current crisis. Solid backing for Israel has long been a centerpiece of US Middle East policy, including support for repeated Israeli assaults and wars on Gaza since the Palestinian elections of 2006. Yet, not even the greatest booster of the slaughter of Palestinians could have dreamed of the unprecedented level of US military and political support that we have seen for this genocide (Bilmes, Hartung, and Semler 2024). In previous Israeli wars on Gaza, US administrations set a deadline or a number of days, weeks, or corpses after which they would force a cessation of the bloodletting. The Biden administration broke that model, and, after forcing a ceasefire so as not to detract from the new president's first weeks in office, the Trump administration was content to allow Israel to continue the daily bombings and massacres until the president brokered the October 10 ceasefire/prisoner exchange agreement, the future of which, however, remains uncertain at the time of this writing.

The point here is that this policy atmosphere – particularly during the first months of the genocide before increasing numbers of Americans began to awaken to the butchery and devastation wrought with their tax dol-

lars – had a terrible impact on campuses.

First, it further exacerbated the long-standing power imbalance in the “public sphere” between pro-Israel and Palestine solidarity activism. Then, as the war quickly morphed into a genocide, increasingly widespread and vocal campus anti-genocide activism emerged and, for the first time, growing numbers of university administrations – in some cases of their own volition, in others, pressured by pro-Israel members of the campus communities, outside organizations with a pro-Israel agenda, and/or state or municipal governments – stepped in to suppress programming and protests, sometimes violently. To find domestic precedents for militarized interventions such as we saw at Columbia or UCLA one would have to go back to the Vietnam war era.

Through the end of the Biden administration there were some, largely performative, attempts to address Islamophobia in the US (The White House 2024), in addition to a much broader push to crack down on anything genocide-deniers called antisemitism.³ At the same time, university administrators and local officials, using the traditional charges of antisemitism or support for terrorism, engaged in a range of actions to criminalize and silence those whose research, teaching, scholarship, or activism sought to focus attention on Gaza.

The Authoritarian Turn

What is different since January 2025 is that

the right-wing Trump administration, allied with many of the same pro-Israel forces that sought to suppress Palestine scholarship and activism under Biden, already had a plan in place for a broad-based, frontal attack on education, science, and academic expertise when it came into office. The charge of antisemitism was simply the first battering ram⁴ to be used – in conjunction with a direct assault on any policies, scholarship, or teaching related to diversity, equity, and inclusion, or “DEI” (Chronicle Staff 2025a). The manual for implementing this program is *Project Esther* (National Task Force to Combat Antisemitism 2024). While framed as targeting antisemitism, *Project Esther* takes aim only at those individuals and groups who are critical of Israel, ignoring the antisemitism inherent in the white Christian nationalism that animates many members of the Trump administration and its supporters. Its program seeks to suppress protest and free speech on campus by targeting faculty and staff, destroying student activist groups, and militarizing campuses. Its goal is to intimidate members of campus communities and beyond to fear for their jobs, visas, and degrees through punishing and criminalizing pro-Palestine advocacy. Its larger project is to silence any communities or movements seeking to protect civil, political, and economic rights, as it destroys centers of critical inquiry in its quest to impose its anti-democratic program.

As the months have passed, we have seen the assault on the universities take myriad devastating forms, in virtually all cases using as

³ The politically motivated and analytically inappropriate pairing of Islamophobia and antisemitism is a topic for another discussion.

⁴ According to a University of Rochester poll conducted in collaboration with UC Berkeley, while 72% of Jewish Americans are concerned about antisemitism on campus, nearly 60% disapprove of the Trump administration’s withholding of federal funding as a means of addressing the issue (Druckman and Fuller 2025). Similarly, many Jewish scholars across the country have rejected the Trump administration’s policy of weaponizing antisemitism. See, for example, Berman, Rosenblatt, and Stahl (2025).

justification spurious charges of rampant antisemitism or insufficient suppression of DEI (Chronicle Staff 2025a). To name some of the most egregious⁵: the sequestering of already appropriated funding for research; the suspension or removal of funding for exchange programs; the imposition of huge fines for purported Title VI violations without benefit of due process; the cancellation of some 6,000 student visas along with multiple cases of brutal arrest, abduction, and detention of anti-genocide activists; the forced resignations of university presidents; threats (as in the case of Harvard) to deny the university the right to seek visas for foreign students; the imposition of a visa ban on a number of African, Middle Eastern, and Asian countries; demands for changes in faculty and student disciplinary processes, admissions criteria, and faculty governance, with the fate of Columbia's Middle East, South Asia and Africa Studies Department the highest-profile example; demands (in the case of UC Berkeley), that the university hand over to the Department of Education the names of faculty, staff, and students who had been accused of involvement in antisemitic incidents; and the replacement of peer review with politicized processes for approving federal grants.

Comparing contexts

Given the increase in gross academic freedom violations we are now witnessing across the US, it is worth reflecting on what attacks on the academy in the MENA region have looked like in comparison. Certainly, control over universities – what they teach, who teaches, who studies there, what research is allowed, and who exercises direct administrative control – has historically been of keen concern to the region's authoritarian regimes.

⁵ For a detailed presentation of the Trump administration's many and various attacks on US universities see Chronicle Staff (2025b).

Among the violations we have become accustomed to seeing are: state interference in the appointment of university faculty, administrators, and leadership; state restrictions on courses of study offered, course materials used, and topics taught; state security force involvement on and near campuses to prevent protests; surveillance and censorship of faculty and students in the classroom, in campus activities, on social media, and in extra-mural speaking and writing; little or no faculty input into university administration and governance; limits on what can be researched and published; restrictions on conference travel and content of participation; interference in university acceptance based on ideological, ethnic, or religious grounds; and dismissal or imprisonment of those who challenge these forms of control. Sadly, we are now witnessing a proliferation of many of these same violations in the US. Indeed, in discussions of creeping authoritarianism, some have drawn parallels between what is happening today in the US and developments in post-2005 Turkey.

That said, we have not (yet) reached fully institutionalized authoritarianism, with the kind of brutality against academics that the Middle East Studies Association (MESA)'s Committee on Academic Freedom has repeatedly written about in Egypt, Iran, Turkey, Bahrain, the UAE and Saudi Arabia. Likewise, though we have seen the increasing securitization of some of our campuses, it pales in comparison to the Israeli occupation's violence in the West Bank, its military assaults against universities, its administrative detention of faculty and students, and its military checkpoints' impairing of physical access to campuses, now against the backdrop of a growing campaign of ethnic cleansing.

Worse, in Sudan – where, on January 7, 2025 the US declared the on-going killing a genocide – Libya, Yemen, Lebanon, Syria, and Iraq, repeated military invasions, attacks, and internal conflicts have taken the lives of tens, hundreds, or thousands of students and faculty in addition to destroying the physical infrastructure and research resources of higher education institutions. And then there is Gaza where, despite the findings of a growing chorus of outraged UN, international human rights, humanitarian relief, legal, and scholarly organizations, the US continues to refuse to declare a genocide, and where the scholasticide (Moody 2025) is an imponderable nightmare.

Navigating the current crisis

In the US, in situations of rights violations, we are accustomed to appealing to established processes, the courts, and the rule of law, although university offices charged with conducting Title VI and Title IX complaints rarely receive high marks. Now, however, the Trump administration has gutted the Department of Education’s Civil Rights Division, while changing the focus of what remains to pursuing charges of antisemitism and violations of its abolition of DEI programs. Moreover, the approach of the Department of Education is now “due process be damned”: accuse first, then strive to break the institution by forcing a settlement in line with the Trump administration’s ideological and financial preferences.⁶

How should we understand the concept of responsibility for protecting academic freedom in this context? First, as I hope this essay has made clear, perhaps the greatest error we

can commit is to (re)act in a way that fails to appreciate that what is being violated goes far beyond our cherished right to study and teach what we choose. As political scientists who study authoritarian regimes, we are particularly well-placed to – and we should – call out the similarities between what we have studied and experienced in the MENA region, and what is happening here in the US. Indeed, we have a special responsibility to explain to others how the administration’s serial attempts at extortion and its flagrant violations of university autonomy are but one part of a multi-pronged attack on American democracy – however deeply flawed – itself.

Administrators, in their eagerness to spare themselves the Trump administration’s wrath and demonstrate their zeal to follow federal or state policies of repression, have often chosen to target the most vulnerable: junior, un- or non-tenured, non-citizen faculty and students, frequently women and men of color. Hence, those of us who are the least vulnerable – senior, tenured, “white,” citizens – have an outsized responsibility to take the lead in demanding respect for academic freedom, speaking out against administrators who prefer conciliation with fascism to fighting it, and defending less well-positioned faculty as well as students. At the same time, as scholars of the region most immediately in the administration’s sights, we have a duty to continue doing what we do: insist upon sovereignty over what we teach in our classes, engage in quality academic programming in our areas of expertise, and provide informed commentary on the myriad threats we face. And in all cases, continue teaching and talking about Palestine.

⁶ The American Council on Education has a website that tracks Trump administration executive orders and actions impacting the Department of Education and higher education more broadly. See American Council on Education (2025).

Upholding or fighting for academic freedom was never just an individual matter.

Now more than ever it is about community and coalitions, both on and off campus. Seek out allies among your colleagues for solidarity and collective action; join your campus branch of AAUP, which has filed numerous lawsuits against the Trump administration and is engaging in broad mobilization across the US; become a member of MESA, if you are not already, as it has taken a leading role in advocacy for our Middle East Studies community and for free speech more broadly.⁷ Most important, do not obey in advance (Snyder 2025) and do not surrender. When you defend your students, you defend all students; when you speak up for a colleague, you defend all our colleagues; and when you insist on your right to teach what you know is most appropriate, you defend all of our rights to do so. Each time you speak out for freedom, whether of expression, for the academy, or from growing authoritarianism at home, you are doing so for all the rest of us, in what is surely the most consequential fight of our lives. ♦

References

American Association of University Professors. n.d. "1940 Statement of Principles on Academic Freedom and Tenure with 1970 Interpretive Comments."

American Council on Education. "Higher Education & The Trump Administration."

Bilmes, Linda J., William D. Hartung, and Stephen Semler. 2024. "Costs of War: United States Spending on Israel's Military Operations and Related U.S. Operations in the Region, October 7, 2023 – September 30, 2024." *Watson Institute for International & Public Affairs*, October 7.

Burns, William J. 2025. "A Letter to America's Discarded Public Servants." *The Atlantic*. August 20.

Berman, Lila Corwin, Kate Rosenblatt, and Ronit Y. Stahl. 2025. "Jewish-Studies Scholars Beware: Trump's Deal Will Corrupt You," *The Chronicle of Higher Education*, September 5.

Chronicle Staff. 2025a. "DEI Legislation Tracker." *The Chronicle of Higher Education*, August 22.

Chronicle Staff. 2025b. "Tracking Trump's Higher-Ed Agenda." *The Chronicle of Higher Education*, October 6.

Cole, Juan. 2025. "Ta-Nahisi Coates: If Democrats can't draw the Line at Genocide, they can't Draw the Line at Democracy." *Informed Comment Blog*, February 20.

Committee on Academic Freedom, Middle East Studies Association. 2022. "Letter to the Department of Education's Office for Civil Rights urging it not to use the IHRA definition of antisemitism and its examples to formulate antidiscrimination regulations," June 27.

⁷ On September 30, Judge William G. Young of the U.S. District Court for the District of Massachusetts ruled in a lawsuit filed by MESA, AAUP, and others, that the Trump administration's policy of arresting, detaining and deporting noncitizen students and faculty for their pro-Palestinian advocacy violated the First Amendment. See "Judge Rules on Lawsuit Regarding First Amendment Rights" (2025).

Committee on Academic Freedom, Middle East Studies Association. 2024. "Letter to the chair and ranking member of the House Committee on Education and the Workforce regarding the committee's investigations of US universities," May 7.

Druckman, James and Bruce Fuller. 2025. "Jewish Americans Worry About Antisemitism, But View Trump's Attack on Universities as Disingenuous, New Poll Shows." *University of California, University of Rochester, and Ipsos*, September.

Fraser, Nancy. 2022. *Cannibal Capitalism: How our System is Devouring Democracy, Care, and the Planet and What We Can Do About It*, New York: Verso.

Dans, Paul and Steven Groves, eds. 2023. *Mandate for Leadership: The Conservative Promise, Project 2025*. Washington, D.C.: The Heritage Foundation.

"Judge Rules on Lawsuit Regarding First Amendment Rights." 2025. *Middle East Studies Association*, September 30.

Lynch, Marc and Shibley Telhami. 2023. "Scholars Who Study the Middle East Are Afraid to Speak Out." *The Chronicle of Higher Education*, December 5.

Middle East Studies Association. 2021. "MESA Board Statement regarding the Working Definition of Antisemitism (and "Contemporary Examples")," March 31.

Moody, Josh. 2025. "What is Scholasticide?" *Inside Higher Ed*, January 14.

National Task Force to Combat Antisemitism. 2024. *Project Esther: A National Strategy to Combat Antisemitism*. Washington, D.C.: The Heritage Foundation.

Sarat, Austin. 2025. "It's Been More Than 50 Years Since the AAUP Revised its Statement on Academic Freedom." *Inside Higher Ed*, August 27.

Schrecker, Ellen. 2025. "Worse Than McCarthyism: Universities in the Age of Trump." *The Nation*, April 3.

Snyder, Timothy. 2025. *On Tyranny: Twenty Lessons From the Twentieth Century*. New York: Crown.

Stanley, Jason. 2018. *How Fascism Works: The Politics of US and Them*. New York: Random House.

Stern, Kenneth S. 2025. "A Bad Deal: By Adopting the IHRA Definition of Antisemitism, Universities are Sacrificing Academic Freedom." *Occasional Paper*, Knight First Amendment Institute at Columbia University, September 5.

The White House. 2024. *The U.S. National Strategy to Counter Islamophobia and Anti-Arab Hate*. Washington, D.C.: The White House.

Militants and Militias: Authoritarian Legacies and the Political Economy of War in Sudan

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Introduction

The ongoing war in Sudan represents, first and foremost, one of the worst humanitarian crises in the world. In just over two years since it began in April 2023, the conflict has resulted in over 13 million displaced persons and approximately 3 million refugees. It has also witnessed a brutal pattern of ethnically targeted killings, sexual violence, and a wide range of atrocities against civilians. Like all wars, it is not, as some analysts have observed, a “nihilistic” war about “nothing” (Applebaum 2025), that is, one absent political, economic, and ideological foundation. Indeed, the war has demonstrated that Sudan is central to understanding some of the most urgent and important themes in the turbulent politics of the Middle East and North Africa. These include the relationship of authoritarianism and civil conflict; the structural and social inequalities underpinning popular mobilization and revolution; the political consequences of the erosion of state capacity in the context of increasingly informalized economies; the rise of para-military militias as key actors in competing attempts at state building; the politics of extraction and critical

minerals in the context of regional instability; and the complicated role of Islamism in domestic and regional politics.

Even prior to 2023, Sudan was one of the most conflict-affected countries in the Middle East and the Horn of Africa. It has long faced multiple challenges, including deep inequality, regional imbalances between center and periphery, subregional armed conflicts, unaccountable governance, and the dominance of the security and para-military militias over the political and economic spheres. In what now appears as a prelude to the war, on October 25, 2021, the country witnessed a military coup that stalled the transition to a civilian democracy, which began in the aftermath of the vibrant 2018 pro-democracy uprising that ousted President Omar al-Bashir. Following the 2021 coup, protests calling for a return to civilian rule continued throughout the country. These protests compelled the country’s military and paramilitary militias, in partnership at the time, to agree to negotiations with the civilian opposition to return the country to a path toward a transition to democracy. However, the negotiations, convened under the auspices of the UN, Saudi Arabia, and the

U.S., under what was termed the “framework agreement,” were woefully unsuccessful. The Sudan Armed Forces (SAF) and the militia led by Mohamed Hamdan Dagalo, known as the Rapid Support Forces (RSF), disagreed over merging the RSF into the regular national standing army, an army that has long been dominated by Islamist cadres appointed by the ousted Bashir regime.

This essay provides a deeper understanding of the root causes of the present war in Sudan by focusing on the legacy of authoritarianism and structural drivers of the war. In doing so, I focus on (1) the nature of the formal and illicit economy upon which the “deep state” was established under the former Islamist regime, (2) internal conflicts in the country reflecting long-standing, historical, social and political divisions, (3) the deeply entrenched military security and coercive parallel security and coercive apparatus, (4) external forces shaping the conflict, (5) and the “logic” of violence as an outcome of rival nascent state building in the context of war.

The Political Economy of War

At the heart of Sudan’s war are two interrelated levels of conflict dating from independence. The first is the power struggle within the Center between groups representing traditional and modern segments of Sudanese civil society. In general terms, conflict in the Center is between the military and groups in civil society linked to the traditional Sufi-led political parties (i.e., the Umma and Democratic Unionist Parties) and Arabized ethnic groups on the one hand, and secular-minded liberals and Islamists on the other. The second level of conflict is between the Center and periphery and is rooted in a long history of unequal distribution of power and wealth along regional, ethnic, and racial lines. This

level is characterized by armed conflicts, including those in Darfur, South Kordofan, and Eastern Sudan. Efforts to consolidate power through the instrumentalization of ethnicity and religion by successive governments, dominated by Arab elites at the Center, characterize the main drivers of conflict in Sudan. In fact, there is wide consensus in the scholarly literature on Sudan that the country’s central political problem is its political elite, and their decision-making and behavior with respect to pivotal national political and economic questions (Khalid 1990; de Waal 2017). Scholars have correctly noted that the challenges facing Sudan are a result of the failure of previous regimes to establish legitimate bureaucratic and economic institutions to resolve the ethnic divisions dating back to the colonial era (Elbattahani 2017). These include a disintegrated state, ongoing conflicts, fragile state institutions, and continuing economic crisis.

A recent report (Mustafa 2022) noted that the ousted Transitional Government inherited a weak economy characterized by widespread corruption and state capture. On the war’s eve, economic activity in Sudan was concentrated in a small number of mostly government companies and, most significantly, upwards of 70% of public sector wages (amounting to 35% of the 2020 budget) went towards the various security and military apparatuses created by the deposed regime (Mustafa 2022, 2). To be sure, at a general level, Sudan’s crisis is the culmination of decades of economic mismanagement in the context of elite political contestation and competition. However, the root causes and evolving dynamics of the war are due to what can be usefully termed a deeply “bifurcated” economy with profound political consequences. More specifically, successive authoritarian regimes utilized the formal as well as the

informal and *illicit* economy as key components to build loyal coalitions in civil society through a system of patron-clientelism: a process which, in the context of shifting domestic and regional economic dynamics, would set the prelude, first to revolution, and then war.

The End of the Oil Boom and the Unraveling of an Authoritarian State

Ultimately, it was the end of the oil boom era which served as a critical juncture in Sudan's history directly resulting in the unraveling of Omar al-Bashir's authoritarian regime. The decline in oil revenue resulting from the 2011 secession of South Sudan led to a deepening of the economic crisis in the country and eroded the state's control over the economy. This, in turn, weakened the former regime's patronage networks, strengthened rivalries among the ruling and militant Islamist National Congress Party's (NCP) leadership, and exacerbated social and economic grievances across a wide spectrum of Sudanese in both urban and rural areas, laying the groundwork for the 2018-2019 popular uprising. Before Sudan's partition in 2011, the formal economy was buttressed by oil which accounted for 50% of domestic revenue and 95% of export earnings. Following the South's secession, Sudan lost 75% of its oil export revenue, resulting in a major deterioration of its fiscal situation (Ministry of Welfare and Social Security, 1-2). It also aggravated the already stark imbalance between center and periphery in social and economic development. According to the Bashir regime's own Ministry of Welfare and Social Security (MWSS) at the time, the loss of oil resulted in cuts to development and federal transfers to the states by 26% and 20%, respectively. It also resulted in the depreciation of the Sudanese pound against the

US dollar, producing a dramatic spike in the average inflation rate, which rose to 42% in the summer of 2011, up from an average of 13% in 2010 (MWSS, 1-2). Moreover, since most food commodities are imported, the rise in inflation worsened poverty levels and impoverished many in the middle class.

It is for these largely structural reasons that the coalition behind the 2018 uprising came to be organized around a wide range of social groups across all regions in the country. The stark decline of oil revenue changed the social and economic landscape and triggered protests largely because the economy had been growing, rather than declining, at a dramatic rate prior to South Sudan's secession. Between 2000 and 2009, real growth in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) averaged 8%. More importantly, in terms of the population's livelihood, per capita income increased from \$776 US in 2004 to \$1,570 US in 2009 (MWSS, 1-2).

But these economic developments also had profound political consequences for state formation and decline. More specifically, the boom period enabled the Islamist-dominated ruling National Congress Party (NCP) to expand its patronage networks in rural and urban areas. In what was a boon period in the building of an Islamist "deep" state, the regime embarked on the creation of state governments across the country and funded thousands of local government bureaucrats. During this period, "Sudan's political economy consolidated around a rentier crony capitalist system, reliant on oil revenues. At the center, it functioned as a centralized kleptocracy and in the far peripheries of southern Sudan, Darfur, South Kordofan, and the Blue Nile (de Waal 2019). Indeed, although the formal economy was expanding, the benefits were unequally distributed. The allocation

of services, employment, and infrastructural projects remained concentrated in Khartoum state and reflected a distinct political logic designed to appease urban constituencies. During most of the 2010s, approximately 60% of development spending was on five major projects located within the central triangle in the North (World Bank 2007, 14). Moreover, while foreign investment expanded during this period it was primarily directed to the oil sector, construction, and services. By contrast, agricultural and other traditional exports were neglected, exacerbating inequality across regional and ethnic cleavages. The legacy of these developments is that they worsened rural poverty and unemployment since upwards of 50% of the rural labor force is engaged in agricultural activities. As of 2009 (a decade before the uprising), the incidence of poverty among the urban and rural populations stood at 26% and 57.6%, respectively. Moreover, figures in this period indicate that poverty levels were far higher in Darfur and the East in comparison with Khartoum and the central states (Ministry of Social Affairs and Security 2012, 13). This deepening inequality across regions and between center and periphery explains the deep-seated grievances in regions such as Darfur and Eastern Sudan and the regional and ethnic nature of the violence associated with the ongoing war.

The Illicit Economy and the Politics of Militancy

If the erosion of the formal economy set the stage for popular mobilization and protest, two sectors of the *informal economy* more directly point to the political dynamics that served as drivers of the war, albeit to different degrees: the parallel market in foreign currency monopolized by militants and the emergence of gold as a key component of the political economy and a principal source

of finance for the RSF (Benson and Makawi 2021). Importantly, the long history of political manipulation of both the informal and formal economy by the Islamists determined the balance of military-civilian relations in favor of the Islamist-dominated SAF. Gaafar Nimeiri (1969-1985) was the first to set the institutional and political foundation of Sudan's present "deep state," linking the domestic economy to military and security interests. However, it was the military authoritarian strategy of *tamkeen* (or empowerment), ushered in by militant Islamists following the 1989 military coup, that fundamentally shaped the character of both state institutions and power dynamics between Sudan's political elite and civil society forces (Bartlett 2020, 46-69). The policy of *tamkeen* contained three essential pillars that served as drivers of conflict by deepening divisions among Sudanese across class, sect, ethnicity, and region in unprecedented ways (Mann 2014, 561-578). The first pillar focused on establishing political and economic hegemony in favor of the Islamist elite organized around the National Islamic Front (NIF) and later the National Congress Party (NCP). This strategy included selling off state-owned enterprises to the Islamist regime's allies, coercing businessmen to grant shares to NCP loyalists, and awarding tax reductions to regime-friendly businesses (Gallab 2008). In a pattern similar to the present, Islamist leaders began the hoarding and selective distribution of commodities such as wheat, sesame seed, gum arabic, and petrol (Khalid 2003). The value of illicit financial flows from Sudan between 1970 and 2008 alone was an astronomical USD \$16 billion, dwarfing that of the formal economy (Kar and Smith 2010). But if the economic policies of *tamkeen* resulted in the Islamists' monopolization of both the formal and informal economic sectors in Sudan, these policies also institutionalized and expanded the SAF's

role in the economy (Verhoeven 2013, 118-140). The creation of the Military Industrial Corporation (MIC) in the early 1990s was a key component that further built the edifice of the “deep state. The MIC granted the SAF practical control over a dozen companies that produced military hardware. SAF’s economic activities later grew beyond the MIC to include a range of civilian industries and sectors (Bartlett 2020, 56; Gallab 2008). The second pillar of *tamkeen* centered on purging the Islamists’ rivals in civil society. Upon assuming power, the Islamist regime, now effectively headed by President Abdel-Fatih Burhan, dismissed thousands of members of the military and the bureaucracy, and banned or coopted labor and trade unions as well as professional associations, gravely weakening civil society actors (Bartlett 202, 51-57). The third pillar, and the one most significant in understanding the nature of the war, was the establishment of militias operating in parallel to the National Army. Under Bashir, the regime utilized these irregular forces to wage a brutal counter-insurgency war against rebels in Darfur while simultaneously deploying them to suppress pro-democracy uprisings in urban areas, including in the capital of Khartoum, throughout the mid to late 2000s. Importantly, this policy was also designed to undermine what was an already weakened national army: an army that historically had been the locus point of a series of coups against incumbent military and civilian regimes throughout Sudan’s post-independence period. Bashir’s regime, having learned from the past, sought to “coup-proof” its rule by eliciting the support from its sponsorship of, and partnership with, a wide range of militias, including, most notably, the *Janjaweed*, which later was transformed into the Rapid Support Forces under the leadership of Mohamed Hamdan Dagalo, known as “Hemed-ti.”

It is against this backdrop that the emergence of the economy as a key arena of political competition and fragmentation following the 2018-19 uprising leading up to the war must be understood. During the transition between 2018 and 2021, two political factions emerged in the Center: the remnants of the NIF’s Islamists coalition linked to members of the NCP who were primarily responsible for building the “deep state” in the 1990s; and a relatively new group (or coalition) composed of SAF leaders as well as the RSF militia now fighting on opposite sides in the war. But whereas in the past the Islamists represented a relatively coherent group, in the transition that followed the revolution, clear fissures emerged between military leaders heading the Transitional Military Council (TMC) and a newly resurgent Islamist ideological group wielding significant control over the security services (Africa Confidential 2020, 1). Tensions between the TMC and the Islamists evolved over time, and this continues as the Islamists continue to exert influence on the Army’s leadership in prosecuting the war and obstructing any reconciliation with either the RSF or civil society groups. These divisions were also evident during the transition. The TMC took control over many large Islamist-owned businesses and curtailed the power of the NISS and even worked towards dismantling several militia forces by confiscating their assets and closing their bank accounts (Africa Confidential 2020, 1). However, even as the TMC and the Islamists competed during the transition, there is significant evidence that both are now working to undermine the pro-democracy movement, prolong the war, and rebuild their political and economic power. One aim of the war is thus to weaken the civilian pro-democracy movement and, in the case of the militant Islamists heading the Army, to *regain* political power and control over the economy and the

state's security apparatus.

Following the October 25, 2021 coup, the TMC, under Burhan, mended relations with the Islamists and NCP, releasing some of the most militant Islamist politicians from prison, reinstating some to the bureaucracy and the state's security apparatus, and generally affording them the opportunity to act as spoilers to any attempt at reconciliation with civilian forces or efforts at mediation sponsored by the international community. Indeed, Burhan continues to be focused on the same objectives he pursued during the now aborted transition, including preserving the SAF's influence over Sudanese civil society and politics; protecting its vast business empire, some of which is now organized as the Defense Industries System (DIS) that replaced the MIC in 2022, but also includes control over business conglomerates involved in construction, mining, pharmaceuticals, and livestock (Africa Confidential 2020); and protecting its formal budget allocation, which makes up a substantial portion of the national budget. A key reason explaining Burhan and the Islamists' motivations in the present war is their opposition to any attempts at dismantling the institutions of the "deep state," which was a key demand of civilian forces during the period of the 2018-19 Revolution. Even as Burhan eliminated the committee to dismantle the assets of the previous regime immediately after the 2021 coup, the leadership of the SAF has continued to insist that all SAF companies are "subject to public reviews, taxes and customs law," arguing that political parties are the ones rejecting regulations [and] accusing civilian politicians, and not the Islamists, of "working to acquire goods, property, and assets of SAF companies and investments for themselves" (Radio Dabanga 2020).

Sudan's economic crisis leading up to the present war can be attributed, to a degree, to SAF companies and investments and the long history of the SAF and the Islamists' manipulation of the informal economy. The threat to these interests is one reason for the October 2021 coup and also the reason militants in the Army have subsequently stalled peace negotiations (Abdelazziz and Eltahir, 2021). However, understanding this crisis requires an analysis of the *mechanisms* utilized to distort and control the domestic economy. Indeed, any deep assessment of the conflict must not only address the nature of the economy but also the mechanisms utilized by the military and Islamist elite to distort, manipulate, and preserve control over the "deep state" at all costs. The SAF collects significant "off the books" funding from its businesses, which increases SAF's independence and undermines other civilian-owned interests, as well as civilian politicians, by depriving them of significant tax revenue. This is because SAF-owned companies continue to benefit from NCP-era policies that exempt them from paying taxes (Bartlett 2020, 48). Furthermore, by operating outside of Sudan's Central Bank, the SAF's involvement in key export sectors like mining, cotton, and gum arabic distorts the balance of trade in these markets. It allows the SAF to directly acquire foreign currency, which enables it to influence Sudan's currency black market in ways that finance its military operations and the security apparatus more generally. This is part of a broader strategy of consolidating control over the economy and depriving non-Islamists access to revenue. Under the NCP regime, the National Intelligence and Security Service (NISS)—which was controlled by the regime's Islamists—also had a large stake in the "deep state" (Musso 2017, 112-128). Consequently, whereas the desire to protect its economic interests is what led to deep fissures

and contestation between Burhan and the civilians in Sudan; intense competition also subsequently emerged between the SAF and Islamist remnants of the previous regime and the para-military militia headed by Mohamed Hamdan Dagolo, whose revenue is generated from the illicit arms and gold trade rather than from the Islamist' "deep states" coffers.

Recruiting Militias: “Conflict” Gold

If the leadership of the Sudanese Army and their Islamist supporters have long relied on the monopolization of state institutions to bolster their economic wealth and political power, another segment of the economy has financed the now-powerful RSF militia, the rival protagonist in Sudan's ongoing war. By the mid-2010s, it was gold rather than oil that came to heavily influence the trajectory of Sudan's political economy. Following the loss of a large proportion of oil revenue in 2011, Omar Bashir turned to gold to bolster his weakened patronage networks. Between 2012 and 2017, gold production increased by an astronomical 141 percent, and by 2018, only a year before the uprising, the country emerged as the world's twelfth largest gold producer (Elbadawi and Suliman 2018). Importantly, benefits accruing from this new gold “boom” are distributed in a far more decentralized fashion than those from oil exports. This is because most gold exports are smuggled illegally, and thus the bulk of the value of gold escapes state coffers. In 2016, one study found this gap equaled US\$4.1 billion, noting that while the Central Bank of Sudan reported gold exports of US\$8.6 billion, its trading partners reported gold imports of US\$12.7 billion (Elbadawi and Suliman 2018). This suggests that the value gap, equaling an enormous 47.7 percent of Sudan's reported gold exports, ends up in private hands.

This not only represented a huge financial loss for the Sudanese government, there is also clear evidence that much of this revenue is captured by members of the military and security establishment, and especially the RSF, which has utilized this lucrative trade as a central recruiting tool to employ fighters against the army, not only in Darfur but throughout the country including in the central state of Gezira and the capital of Khartoum.

Importantly, the transition from oil to gold has shifted the country's political economy from a more centralized oil-based patronage system towards a more fractured system whereby rents, derived from gold smuggling, are utilized to fund the recruitment of irregular militia forces has come to play a central role. It is for this reason that analysts have described Sudan's political economy as increasingly decentralized and characterized by a “shadow economy”; a situation where a multitude of interests and actors now vie for resources, rents, and markets, characterizing the nature of state failure and the country's armed conflict. The gold mining sector is an important illustrative case of this decentralized but nevertheless coherently organized sector with important political consequences for the present war. This sector can essentially be divided along three dimensions: artisanal mining, small-scale mining, and large-scale production (United Nations Trade and Development-UNCTAD 2016). The most significant of these is the artisanal sector, which consists of unprocessed mining, known locally as “gharabeel.” It is dominated by the Rashaida tribe in Kassala State on the borders of Eritrea along the Red Sea, but this type of production also spans the Blue Nile, River state, Northern State, Kassala, and South Kordofan states. This sector accounts for approximately 85% of total production and

is responsible for 90% of all gold smuggled outside of the country. It can be characterized as informal because it is unlicensed by the government and does not contribute to government tax revenue. In other words, it largely evades the government's efforts to redirect profits from this sector to the central bank, and its mode of operation and decentralized nature underpins the unraveling of the state from Sudanese society in ways that now threaten to lead to the de facto, if not de jure, division of the country.

Conflict or Cooperation: The Role of External Actors

While the primary dynamics driving conflict in Sudan are internal, regional actors and other players further afield play influential roles. Sudan's current crisis must be understood within the broader configuration of relations in its region. This includes the Gulf, the Horn of Africa, and particularly the Red Sea, and reflects intense rivalries and competing interests among Middle Eastern states and the countries in the Horn of Africa, and particularly Ethiopia. Over the last two decades, Saudi Arabia, the UAE, and to a lesser extent Qatar and Turkey, all have increased their engagement in the Red Sea (United Institute of Peace 2020, 1-60). The Gulf states have economic as well as strategic interests vis-à-vis Sudan. Sudan has long been perceived as a potential "breadbasket" by Gulf states with great potential for investment in land and agriculture. They also clearly consider the Horn of Africa critical in their struggle against Iran, which they perceive as an "existential threat" (United Institute of Peace 2020). Saudi Arabia and the UAE have long worried about Iranian encirclement through the Straits of Hormuz and Bab el-Mandeb (Medani 2012, 12-30). These concerns were further heightened by Iranian

support for the Houthi movement in Yemen, which led to military intervention by a Saudi-led coalition in 2015.

The Gulf states also have economic interests in the Red Sea. Both the Emirates and Saudi Arabia have developed ports and established military bases in the region. The UAE has a base in Eritrea (Assab), while Saudi Arabia has signed an agreement for a base in Djibouti. Ideological issues are also significant with respect to the Gulf's relationship with Sudan. Saudi Arabia, the UAE, and Egypt continue to be wary of an Islamist coalition heading the Sudanese government. All three would like to limit the Muslim Brotherhood's influence in the region, while Qatar and Turkey are more supportive of Islamism. The Egyptian-Sudanese relationship cooled after the 2013 military coup against President Morsi because Cairo accused the ousted Bashir regime of providing a haven and even training Brotherhood members escaping Egypt (United States Institute of Peace 2020, 1-60).

An even more important issue for Egypt concerns tensions over the Nile River. In 2020, Ethiopia started filling the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (GERD), a US\$ 4.8 billion hydroelectric dam on the Blue Nile. This has transformed relations between Egypt and its upstream neighbors (United States Institute of Peace 2020, 27). Officials in Addis Ababa argue the GERD will have no major impact on water flow to both Sudan and Egypt. They argue instead that the Dam will not only provide affordable electric power to Ethiopia (and potentially other states); it would also provide the necessary water sources so crucial to managing the problem of recurring droughts in the region. Egypt, on the other hand, insists that the GERD will reduce its supply of water and continues to try to secure a political agreement over the timetable for

filling the GERD's reservoir in a way that would minimize the adverse effects to its own population and development plans (United States Institute of Peace 2020, 27).

For its part, even as the war continues, the de facto government headed by Burhan is caught between competing Egyptian and Ethiopian interests. From Sudan's perspective, the GERD would enable the country to use more water from its own allocation, instead of allowing this water to flow downstream to Egypt. It would also end the seasonal fluctuations of the Blue Nile and allow for the expansion of agriculture, thereby permitting two or three crop rotations every year instead of one. Yet, fear lingers that the GERD could threaten the safety of Sudan's own dams and make it more difficult for the government to manage its own development projects. Prior to the war, both Egypt and Ethiopia had tried to sway Sudan towards their respective positions, which, according to reports, had deepened factionalism within Khartoum's transitional government (Mbaku 2020). For its part, the United States continues to voice support for an end to the war and a peaceful transition to democracy in Sudan. Moreover, while Egypt, the UAE, and Saudi Arabia were quick to support Abdel-Fatih al-Burhan following his coup in 2021, Saudi Arabia has now partnered with the U.S. in the latter's efforts to broker an agreement that is calling for a cease-fire and a transition to a civilian-led government. More recently, on September 12, 2025, the US sponsored talks over Sudan, bringing together the most important external actors to the war: Saudi Arabia, Egypt, and the UAE. While this is an encouraging sign, there is clear evidence that competing interests remain. Egypt and Saudi Arabia continue to support Sudan's military ostensibly to safeguard their strategic interest in the region as well as to forestall a democratic tide

in the country, and simultaneously weaken the influence of the Muslim Brotherhood. It remains unclear whether the US, the Gulf states, and Egypt will be able to bridge the violent rivalry between Burhan and Hemedti. Hemedti enjoys close relations with Abu Dhabi, based on their economic relations and cooperation during the Yemen war, and has a wide network of fighters in Libya and Chad. The war has clearly shown that Hemedti has personal ambitions that pit him against Burhan and the SAF.

War, the “Deep State”, and the threat of democracy

Ultimately, however, what undermined the transition to democracy was the previous government's inability to dismantle the vestiges of the vast financial empire wielded by the security sector and the military. Indeed, prior to the war several analysts noted that the biggest risk to Sudan lay in the financial power of the military heading the transitional government at the time. As noted above, the military and the security apparatus control companies involved in oil, gum arabic, sesame, weapons, fuel, wheat, telecommunications, banking, real estate, and gold. The military's defense companies produce a vast array of consumer goods and retain a large share of the country's banking institutions. Moreover, if the military controls large sectors of the economy, the RSF also benefits from subsidies, which allow it and the SAF to hoard commodities and profit from their sale in the black market at inflated prices to consumers. While accurate data is difficult to obtain, there is some evidence to suggest that the Military controls companies such as al-Fakher, as-Sobat, and SIN, which dominate the market in fuel and wheat. According to one report, the SAF controls 60% of the market in wheat, although Sudanese sources have

noted that former NCP businessmen continue to wield the greatest influence in these markets (Resnick 2021).

These rents - generated from military-state predation - are used by Burhan to dole out patronage to Islamist-allied forces in the Army. These are the same loyal clients Omar Bashir patronized and supported prior to his ouster in 2019 (Medani 2022). Nevertheless, while a focus on the military and security apparatus' power over civil society is warranted, what is missing in analysis of Sudan's "deep state" is an examination of the political and economic factors that have worked to sustain the patronage system in the first place; a system forged under Bashir and now exploited by Burhan and Hemedti, albeit for different political objectives.

Consequently, at the root of the tragic war is the legacy of an illegitimate and authoritarian central authority and weak political institutions. Gold smuggling, discussed in detail above, is an illustrative example of both the challenges of Sudan's "deep state" as well as the prospects for strengthening institutions in ways that promote good governance. Indeed, if the combination of weak regulatory and legal institutions has fueled the informal and illicit smuggling of the nation's gold resources and provided financing for militia-led violence and war, they have also posed a direct challenge to a transition to civilian rule or negotiated peace. This is primarily because the trade has benefited the interests of the military and security forces rather than Sudanese civil society. Since Bashir's overthrow in April 2019, along with the head of the army, Abdul Fattah al-Burhan, it is Mohamed Hemedti Hamdan Dagolo, the RSF leader, who has wielded disproportionate control over the country's now failed transition. Like Burhan and his allies, Hemedti and his militia saw

the potential of Sudanese democracy as a grave threat to their political power and vast wealth. It is for these reasons that both are standing in the way of international efforts at mitigating conflict, negotiating a cease-fire, and building a sustainable peace.

War Making as State Making: The Struggle for Sudan

While in the first two years of the war in Sudan the conflict primarily represented a rivalry between a para-legal militia and the Sudan Armed Forces, in its current manifestation it is best described as a violent contest between two forms of state-building efforts. In the summer of 2025, the RSF announced the establishment of a parallel government based in the city of Nyala in South Darfur to rival the de facto government led by General Burhan in the eastern city of Port-Sudan on the Red Sea. Consequently, Sudan now represents two de facto political entities, each seeking to build new states from scratch: one that seeks to build a state on the edifice of the former Islamist authoritarian state; the other, seeking to form, through brutal violence against civilians, a governance structure ostensibly built on a secular and non-racial government of "unity and peace." Both have already enacted citizenship measures and announced a new currency designed to restrict the right to citizenship to only those Sudanese in areas under their respective control, while simultaneously demarcating new economic borders in their nascent efforts at state-building.

Sudan's evolving political economy and particularly the erosion of the state's formal extractive capacity, combined with the absence of an autonomous and legitimate national standing army, are two principal factors that have resulted in the worst humanitarian crisis in the world. These two issues will continue

to determine the relative success of the ongoing state-building efforts. This, in turn, will determine whether Sudan will retain its territorial integrity or splinter as occurred with South Sudan in 2011.

The evidence suggests that, absent a resolution to the war, it is unlikely there will be a formal separation. The RSF does not have the legitimacy among the population it controls and, importantly, it does not have the mechanisms of revenue generation that would culminate in state consolidation (Tilly 1985). For its part, the SAF, is similarly burdened by a lack of legitimacy because of the authoritarian policies of the Islamist regime. Perhaps more importantly, the SAF is riven with divisions between Islamist stalwarts and the rank-and-file officers are divided along ethnic lines. Equally important is that while the Army has strong support from regional powers more interested in a reliable military alliance than the democratic aspirations of the Sudanese population, they are nevertheless cautious about the influence and power Islamists still wield among the upper echelons of the SAF leadership.

Understanding the current dynamics of war as a contest between two rival military and political actors waging war and extracting revenue, albeit through violent means, in order to build new states also helps to explain the logic and severity of the mass-scale violence against civilians. For its part, the RSF has used windfall profits from the gold trade and its strategic alliance with the UAE to expand its recruitment drives and to wage war against the civilian population, even as it battles its former partners among the SAF leadership. At the time of writing, the RSF controls most of the provinces of Darfur and has waged a brutal siege of the northern Darfur capital of al Fasher. There is clear evidence

that, as with most insurgent militias (Jentzch 2015; Weinstein 2006), RSF forces are motivated by material and strategic objectives rather than ideology. However, this is not the case with its rival and the architect of Sudan's war. Over the course of the war, the more militant remnants of the Islamist National Congress Party have managed to wield disproportionate influence over the upper echelons of the military establishment and especially the high-ranking officers that make up the powerful Security and Intelligence Committee. These stalwarts of the Islamist movement are intent on pursuing the war with the view that anything short of a military victory would usher in an era of civilian or militia-led rule that would ultimately oust them from authority and state power. It is for this reason, that following the October 2021 coup, General Burhan released some prominent Islamist militants from prison, appointed them to high political office, and has generally allowed them to act as spoilers in attempts at reconciliation with civilian forces or efforts at mediation sponsored by the US and Saudi Arabia – and more recently, the Quad, made up of the US, Saudi Arabia, Egypt and the UAE. Moreover, as students of insurgent politics have long observed, in contexts where nascent state builders and their allied militias are unable to provide protection, administer justice, and collect taxes to fund social programs generating legitimacy for their cause, they frequently resort to severe forms of mass violence against civilians so as to “punish their enemies and sanction behavior through extreme forms of violence,” sometimes going as far as to utilize food and sexual violence as weapons of war (Stanton 2015; Kalyvas 2006).

Conclusion

If the roots of the war in Sudan are rooted in decades of authoritarian rule and the mili-

tarization of politics, an important obstacle to a cessation of hostilities and long term political stability has to do with the country's strategic and financial dependence on regional actors. The prospect of successful state building, wherein domestic sources of revenue are captured and allocated in the service of consolidating politico-military rule and providing a modicum of public goods to the population, are in this instance undermined by the exigencies of regional constraints and interventions. Both the RSF and the SAF are greatly dependent on external rather than local revenue sources, whether to fund their war campaigns or build durable and legitimate institutions in their respective territories. Taken together, these factors preclude the generation of domestic or international legitimacy that is so crucial to achieving peace and stability for Sudan. What is at stake for the region is also consequential. Bordering seven countries, the Sahel region, and the contested Red Sea, the continuation of the Sudanese war threatens the long-term strategic and economic interests of several countries in the region. It threatens Egypt's interests over the Nile waters and its contested southern frontier; Turkey and Saudi Arabia's ambitions over the Red Sea region; Iran's efforts to influence developments in the region through its military support of Burhan; and UAE's long-term vision for their investments in Sudan and Africa.

Consequently, for students of the political science of the Middle East and North Africa, Sudan is an important case for the study of a variety of themes central to the politics of region. It allows for the examination of the role of authoritarian legacies and the roots of war; an understanding of the precarious balance between military-civil relations that can result in popular revolution, as well as fatal reversals resulting in deep seated conflicts

as in Syria; the logic and patterns of violence associated with divided and rival efforts at state building as in Libya and Somalia; the dynamics underpinning the transformation of para-legal militias into an autonomous force waging war against its former partners at the level of the state; and the relationship between Islamist political ideology and rule in countries in the region divided along ethnic, racial and sectarian cleavages. ♦

References

- Abdelaziz, Khalid and Nafisa Eltahir. 2021. "Sudan task force chasing Bashir-era assets sees progress, faces criticism, *Reuters*, April 6.
- Africa Confidential. 2020. "Burhan lets Islamists back in." 63 (10), June 25.
- Applebaum, Anne. 2025. "The Most Nihilistic Conflict on Earth." *The Atlantic*. August 6, 2025.
- Bartlett, Anne L. 2020. "Dismantling the 'Deep State' in Sudan," *Australasian Review of African Studies* 41 (1): 49-69.
- Benson, Mathew and Raga Makawi. 2021. "The 'Real Politics' of Taxation in Post-Revolutionary Sudan." January 18.
- De Waal, Alex. 2019. "Sudan: A Political Marketplace Framework of Analysis." Occasional Paper no. 19, World Peace Foundation: Conflict Research Programme, August.
- Elbadawi, Ibrahim and Khalid Suliman. 2018. "The Macroeconomics of the gold economy in Sudan." Economic Research Forum (ERF) Working Paper 1203.

- Elbattahani, Atta. 2017. "Sudan: Transition to Democracy After 2011, a Dismembered State Navigating Uncertainties." In *Democratic Transitions in the Arab World*, edited by Ibrahim Elbadawi, and Samir Makdisi, 269–305. Cambridge University Press.
- Eriksen, Stein Sundstol. 2005. "The Congo War and the Prospects for State Formation: Rwanda and Uganda Compared," *Third World Quarterly* 26 (7): 1097-1113.
- Gallab, Ahmed. 2008. *The First Islamic Republic: Development and Disintegration of Islamism in Sudan*. Surrey: Ashgate.
- Kar, Dev, and Devon Cartwright-Smith. 2010. *Illicit Financial Flows from Africa: Hidden Resource for Development*. Global Financial Integrity. Washington DC.
- Ibrahim, M.S. Ibrahim. 2016. "Artisanal mining in Sudan-opportunities, challenges, and impacts." United Nations Trade and Development (UNCTAD). United Nations Conference on Trade and Development presentation at the 17th Africa Oil, Gas and Mines Trade and Finance Conference and Exhibition, Khartoum, Sudan. Unpublished paper.
- Jentsch, Corinna, Stathis Kalyvas, and Livia Schubiger. 2015. "Militias in Civil Wars." *Journal of Conflict Resolution* 59 (5): 755-769.
- Kalyvas, Stathis. 2006. *The Logic of Violence in Civil War*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Khalid, Mansour. 2003. *War and Peace in Sudan*. London: Keagan Paul.
- _____. 1990. *The Government They Deserve: The Role of the Elite in Sudan's Political Evolution*. Cambridge University Press.
- Mann, Laura. 2014. "Wasta! The long-term implications of education expansion and economic liberalisation on politics in Sudan," *Review of African Political Economy*. 41(14): 561-578.
- Mbaku, John Mukum Mbaku. 2020. "The Conflict over the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam." *Brookings Institutions*, August 5.
- Medani, Khalid. 2012. "Sudan in the Shadow of the Cold War," *Journal of North African Studies*. 17(2): 275-294.
- _____. 2022. *Black Markets and Militants: Informal Networks in the Middle East and Africa*. Cambridge University Press, 2nd edition.
- Ministry of Social Welfare and Security. 2012. The National Population Council. *Draft Report: "The Millennium Development Goals (MDGs): Status, Challenges and Prospects for Sudan."* Khartoum, Sudan, March.
- Mustafa, Nada. 2019. "Stubborn Historical Legacies: Power Relations and Government Policy in Sudan." *Economic Research Forum (ERF) Working Paper No. 1551*, May 2022.
- Musso, Giorgio. 2017. "Sudan and the unbearable lightness of Islamism: From revolution to rentier authoritarianism." *The International Spectator* 52 (4): 112-128.
- Radio Dabanga. 2020. "El Burhan defends role of Sudan Armed Forces in the economy." August 24.

Resnick, Daniel. 2021. "Political Economy of Food Value Chains in Post-Revolutionary Sudan." IFPRI, Strategy Support Program, Working Paper 01, October.

Schubert, Jon, Ulf Engle, and Elisio Macamo. 2018. "Introduction: Boom and bust: extractive industries and African states in the twenty-first century." In *Extractive Industries and Changing State Dynamics in Africa: Beyond the Resource Curse*, 1-18. London: Routledge, Taylor & Francis.

Stanton, Jessica. 2015. "Regulating Militias: Governments, militias, and civilian targeting in civil war." *Journal of Conflict Resolution* 59 (5): 899-923.

Tilly, Charles. 1985. "War Making and State Making as Organized Crime." In *Bringing the State Back In*, eds. Peter B. Evans, Dietrich Rueschemeyer, and Theda Skocpol. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

United States Institute of Peace. 2020. "Final Report and Recommendations of the Senior Study Group of Peace and Security in the Red Sea Arena," USIP, Washington, DC.: 1-64.

Verhoeven, Harry. 2013. "The rise and fall of Sudan's Al-Ingaz Revolution: the transition from militarized Islamist to economic salvation and the Comprehensive Peace Agreement." *Civil Wars* 15 (2): 118-140.

Weinstein, Jeremy. 2006. *Inside Rebellion: The Politics of Insurgent Violence*. Cambridge University Press.

World Bank. 2007. "Sudan public expenditure review: synthesis report." World Bank Report no. 41840-SD. Washington DC. December.

Research Symposium: Syria in Transition: Reconstructing State, Society, and Sovereignty

Introduction by Rana B. Khoury and Sefa Secen

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The fall of Bashar al-Asad in December 2024 marked a historic rupture in Syria's modern history. After more than thirteen years of revolution and civil war, the country now faces the immense task of reconstruction. Yet as the contributions in this symposium make clear, rebuilding Syria is not only about bricks and mortar. It is a profoundly political process, entangled with questions of sovereignty, state-society relations, displacement, social hierarchy, and justice. The very meaning of "reconstruction" remains unsettled: will it foster durable institutions and social trust, or merely reproduce coercion, exclusion, and dependency under new guises?

These critical questions are being posed in a highly unfavorable context. For half a cent-

ury, Hafiz al-Asad and then his son Bashar invoked methods of violent and hegemonic authoritarian rule that forbade dissent and eroded ties between Syrians and between Syria and the outside world. Since the 1990s, they also pulled back the socialist policies that had supported the well-being of ordinary Syrians; the middle class retreated with the state, even as the elite enriched themselves. When faced with a popular movement amid the wave of "Arab Spring" uprisings in 2011, the regime unleashed force rather than reform and initiated one of the most brutal wars of the twenty-first century. In the war's course, hundreds of thousands perished, millions were displaced, territory was fragmented, infrastructure crumbled, sanctions strangled, extremists thrived, and external

aactors had their way with the pieces.

It is difficult to fathom how peace and prosperity can possibly follow, even as Syrians desperately hope for and deserve better.

As particular as these challenges appear to be for Syria, our contributors have all reminded us that political science has dealt with similar questions before. Embedding their analyses in existing literature on post-conflict processes, democratization, forced migration, transitional justice, and international intervention, they help us anticipate the challenges—and possibilities—ahead.

One recurring theme is the struggle to re-imagine the relationship between rulers and ruled. Tiina Hyyppä emphasizes that while Asad's fall raised hopes for a new social contract based on trust, the interim government has at times leaned on coercive practices that echo the authoritarian past. Violence in Sweida and the exclusionary drafting of a transitional constitution illustrate how fragile the foundations of trust remain. This echoes Salam Said's description and analysis of the transitional leadership under Ahmed al-Sharaa. Her contribution shows that promises of inclusivity are belied by exclusive institution-building in politics, society, and the economy. The Syrian state, as such, is at stake.

The external dimension of reconstruction is equally fraught. Sumaya Malas traces how Bashar al-Asad's survival was propped up by foreign patrons who traded military and political backing for slices of Syria's economy. She warns that the new wave of Gulf investment carries similar risks: if reconstruction contracts are captured by elites and foreign partners rather than routed through transparent institutions, Syria may once again sacrifice sovereignty for short-term stability.

This theme of fragility is also evident in Sefa Secen's contribution, which interrogates return movements in the process of transition. He discusses how returns are uneven, fragile, and often temporary, reflecting localized security conditions and shifting host-state pressures. Counting returns, he argues, is not a straightforward sign of stability but a window into the churn of displacement and remigration that will likely define Syria's future.

Reconstruction is also reshaping Syria's social fabric in ways that risk entrenching new hierarchies. Ammar Shamaileh highlights how revolutionary legitimacy may be producing a privileged class with connections to the ruling elite and state resources, forged through wartime residence and revolutionary participation. Emily Scott, in turn, situates these dynamics within broader questions of justice and accountability and considers the international and local actors that may be involved in post-conflict processes. She cautions that without genuine transitional justice and survivor-led accountability, reconstruction will remain hollow and peace elusive.

These contributions reveal the challenges of Syria's transition. They also highlight pathways forward: rebuilding trust, reclaiming sovereignty, creating inclusive institutions, and centering justice. By foregrounding these perspectives, this symposium aims to spark scholarly and policy conversations about what reconstruction in Syria means and for whom. As the country enters this new chapter, the stakes could not be higher: whether Syrians will inherit another brittle and fierce order or lay the foundation for a more just and inclusive future. ♦

From Rule of Violence to Rule of Trust? State-Society Relations in Post-Asad Syria

Tiina Hyypä

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The overthrow of Bashar al-Asad was a monumental rupture in Syria's history, permitting a new beginning for the country. As Syrians are rebuilding their country, the relations between the new rulers and the ruled will be redrawn. Asad-era and wartime rule relied heavily on violence and coercion. Asad's fall had raised hopes that those practices would be over, and a new social contract based on trust could emerge. Now, more than half a year since Asad's toppling, the new social contract is still in the making, and trust is wearing down.

Social contracts create “a degree of certainty in the expectations of all involved parties [here: society and the state] about what they must give and receive” (Loewe et al. 2024, 2). Such contracts underpin trust between the parties and stabilize state-society relations. Whereas the Asad-era social contract was placed from above on the people, Asad's fall is a critical juncture that offers a potential for change where a social contract could truly be negotiated between the society and the state. I argue that for a new social contract that does not rely on violence to emerge, trust between the state and the people needs to be created first.

¹ A social contract, along which people's subjugation and/or loyalty was traded for social services and public employment existed, at least in theory, as well, but began to increasingly erode after Bashar al-Asad took power and commenced neoliberal economic policies.

Thus, while Syrians are facing yet another uncertain situation, they need to learn to trust each other. Trust between the ruler and the people needs to be renegotiated in the post-Asad society. Based on their history during the uprising and war, it will not be easy, although it is not an impossible task. Until now, the new rulers have shown trust mainly through words, and they have yet to demonstrate it in action. Without it, it will be difficult for individuals to trust the new authorities and commit to a social contract. If violent and authoritarian practices continue, distrust will likely increase. I analyze here two concerning processes, one related to increasingly centralized powers and the other a form of coercive rule, that have hampered people's trust in the new ruler and have the potential to rapidly undermine the fragile rebuilding of the nation.

Coercion and violence, “a modality of government” that structured and ordered relations between the Syrian rulers and the people (Ismail 2018), was a central tool for the authoritarian regimes of Hafiz (1970–2000) and Bashar al-Asad (2000–2024).¹ While political powers were centralized in the president and the Ba'ath party, the four different intelligence services managed a bureaucracy

of torture, and through surveillance monitored the society (Akdedian 2024, 57). Trust between the ruler and the ruled – or among the people – was not part of the social contract; instead, mistrust was used for the regime to stay in power: ordinary people were recruited as informants, and anyone could be imprisoned without trial and face severe torture and death. Hence, trust existed only among small, intimate networks: family and friends.

After the Syrian uprising erupted in early 2011, local forms of trust emerged among people. This was remarkable as the authoritarian regime had for decades used the authoritarian tools of divide and rule. For activists taking part in the revolution, networks of trust expanded and took new forms; friends of friends got to know each other, and revolutionary activists came together and organized for a common goal: toppling the Asad regime.

As the uprising militarized and the war went on, armed groups became more and more powerful and, again, violence became the mode of governance: mass violence orchestrated by the regime was avenged with violence on perceived loyalist communities; movement was controlled by armed groups, preventing travel for many; and economic activities were increasingly supervised by those with arms. Trust played a role in some of these networks as well, when military groups used their familiar networks to recruit, or when civilians used their intimate links to fighters to carve out space for nonviolent action. Following the uprising's militarization, Syria split into several parts. The divisions were not only entirely based on sectarian lines, although these were intentionally emphasized by different parties, fuelling sectarian tensions and grievances which now have

to be mended.

After Bashar al-Asad was overthrown, many celebrated the end of his violent, authoritarian rule. The interim president, Ahmed al-Sharaa, although originating from an Islamist armed group, Hayat Tahrir al-Sham (HTS), has tried to gain people's trust by emphasizing unity and that the new Syria "is for all Syrians" (Al Jazeera 2025). Since December 2024, Damascus has worked, and on many occasions, succeeded in having sanctions imposed on Syria lifted and in improving the living conditions through new commercial and energy agreements with regional countries. While material reconstruction is important, it alone will not create the trust that is needed between ruler and ruled. Although many of those revolutionary activists that mobilized in 2011 did not support HTS during the war, they remained optimistic that things could turn out better than under Asad. However, for many members of religious and ethnic minorities, potential Islamist rule generated fears of an uncertain future.

Besides rehabilitating foreign policy and the economy, the transitional government is drafting the new social contract, too. It has created political institutions in a rapid manner, before any real nationwide discussions on the topics. The transitional constitution, decreed without public consultation or elections, gives extensive powers to the president, for example, the right to appoint a third of the People's Assembly's members directly. In addition, it fails to create accountability mechanisms and lacks judicial independence (Enab Baladi 2025). Such powers, in force for a five-year transitional period, could cement al-Sharaa's rule beyond this period and ease the return to authoritarian rule. Syrian political thinker Yassin al-Haj Saleh has called such centering of powers "centralist extremist

tendencies” (Al-Haj Saleh 2025).

On a more symbolic level, the president revealed the new emblem for Syria, a gold-en eagle, which symbolizes the unity of the country and the new contract between the people and the state. This amendment, too, was done in closed circles. These changes show how the transitional authorities are already making profound changes on practical and symbolic levels and creating a new Syria of *their* vision. If powers are concentrated in the hands of a small clique, reminiscent of the Asad-era regime, sharing those powers later on will be difficult.

Despite the severity of these changes, a more serious problem has been the large-scale violence that minorities, especially, have faced. The violent events on the coast in March 2025 where over 1600 people, most of them 'Alawites, were killed (Syrian Network for Human Rights 2025a) decreased the little (if any) trust minorities had towards the new rulers, increasing fear that all minorities might be victims of violence in the future.

Some of those fears materialized in July when clashes broke out in as-Sweida governorate initially between local Bedouin tribes and Druze groups. The Syrian General Security was sent to the area to restore order, but many saw this as Damascus’s attempt to coercively take over the governorate, and violence increased. During the first eleven days, over 800 people, civilians and fighters, were killed (Syrian Network for Human Rights 2025b). Adding a regional dimension to the fighting, Israel claimed to protect the Druze and conducted air strikes against General Security forces in Sweida and sites in Damascus. All parties have been accused of violations, and Damascus has ordered an investigation into the events (Danon and Al Nofal 2025). What

is also damning for the new rulers are the human rights violations that their own forces (and fighters with unmarked military attire) have committed – after all, government forces should protect citizens. As had been the case with earlier violent instances, this time authorities cannot claim that their unruly supporters were behind the atrocities. In this instance, President al-Sharaa endorsed large-scale tribal mobilization, which only increased violence (Pinfold and Hammoud 2025). Furthermore, reports of besieged Sweida city bring back images of Asad-style collective punishments of restive areas.

Events in Sweida and the government’s use of coercive power resemble the wartime practices of how power and order were created and preserved, and are darkly reminiscent of Asad-era modes of governance. The events have changed how many ordinary Syrians who want to work for the new country see the new rulers. It can clearly be seen as a watershed moment for post-Asad Syria that has polarized the country further along sectarian and regional lines.

The opposite of trust is distrust. It can manifest as fear or anger, simmering beneath the surface, or in open and violent ways. There are large amounts of weapons available in Syria, and during the war, many disputes were settled with arms. Therefore, if trust is not built, violence can, and will, remain an essential part of the social norms through which communities navigate post-Asad realities. If violence is the means through which communities are ruled and individuals seek to protect themselves against that violence, then Syria will not be united and could even spiral into a renewed and unfettered conflict.

Just as experiences and memories of violence affected ruler-ruled relations and those be-

tween the people during the Asad eras (Ismail 2018, 22), so do wartime and postwar experiences and memories construct relations that are (re)built now. The events of Sweida have shown that transition into a new Syria cannot happen either top down or by force. The rulers have to build trust through their actions, for example, by better including the people in the statebuilding process, investigating violent events in a transparent manner, and holding those who have committed violations accountable. Everyone needs to be included in the making of the new social contract. Alongside this, the security forces need to provide real security to all. But conventional security sector reform alone will never be sufficient. Supporting local initiatives that rebuild communities and create trust between individuals is the crucial step; from this basis, a genuine engagement between ruler and ruled can be built. The importance of trust is manifest and should be central to the process of Syrian reconstruction and statebuilding, but it is a slow, painstaking, and deliberate process that requires dialogue, empathy, understanding, and solidarity. ♦

References

Akdedian, Harout. 2024. *State Atrophy in Syria. War, Society and Institutional Change*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.

Al-Haj Saleh, Yassin. 2025. "The Syrian Conflict Is Not Yet Over. Assad Has Fallen, But the Revolution Hasn't Won." *Aljazeera*, April 30.

Aljazeera. 2025. "Syria's President Calls for Unity and Rebuilding at a National Dialogue Conference in Damascus." February 25.

Al-Jeratli, Khaled. 2025. "Syrian Constitutional Declaration: Controversy over Identity and Presidential Powers." *Enab Baladi*, March 17.

Danon, Natacha and Walid Al Nofal. 2025. "Is There a Road Forward for Suwayda's Druze and Damascus?" *Syria Direct*, July 25.

Ismail, Salwa. 2018. *The Rule of Violence. Subjectivity, Memory and Government in Syria*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Loewe, Markus et al. 2024. "Drivers of Change in Social Contracts: Building a Conceptual Framework." *Mediterranean Politics*, 1–27.

Pinfold, Rob Geist and Hussam Hammoud. 2025. "How Syria's New Government Risks Undermining Itself." *Middle East Council on Global Affairs*, August 2.

Syrian Network for Human Rights. 2025a. "Daily Update: Toll of Extrajudicial Killings That Took Place in the Wake of the Events in the Syrian Coastal Region between March 6 and March 10, 2025." April 15.

Syrian Network for Human Rights. 2025b. "Update of Latest Toll: At least 814 Syrians Have Been Killed and More than 903 Others Injured in Suwayda Governorate since July 13." July 24.

Not for Sale: Post-Conflict Reconstruction and Reclaiming Syrian Sovereignty After Asad

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The Syrian civil war was defined by several foreign actors' interventions (Phillips 2020). The Asad regime's survival depended heavily on foreign support, particularly the Russian military intervention that began in 2015. Iran, China, and Hizbullah also provided critical assistance, while the United States, Türkiye, and Gulf states funded opposition groups, further fragmenting the battlefield. By mid-2024, approximately 801 foreign military sites were dispersed across the country, indicating the large extent of foreign entanglement in Syria that eroded Syrian sovereignty (Action on Armed Violence 2024).

As Syria undergoes a fragile political transition under President Ahmad al-Sharaa, this legacy of foreign domination and institutional decay continues to shape the country's trajectory. The new government faces the daunting task of reconstituting state capacity while disentangling national sovereignty from external tutelage. This post-conflict moment offers a narrow but critical opportunity: to centralize authority in order to stabilize governance, while simultaneously rebuilding institutions and infrastructure through international assistance that respects Syrian sovereignty. Equally vital is the need to

expand civil society to nurture a civic political culture rooted in domestic participation rather than foreign patronage. To move Syria forward, policymakers must prioritize restoring institutional coherence, reinforcing the state's autonomy, and cultivating public trust through inclusive, accountable governance that is resilient to external interference.

The Legacies of Foreign Support: The Dictator's (Former) Friends

Syria has been the arena of overlapping and often competing foreign interventions that have profoundly shaped the trajectory of the Asad regime and the Syrian state. Russia intervened militarily in 2015 to shore up the Asad government, providing airpower, strategic coordination, and diplomatic cover, which decisively altered the balance of power on the ground (Allison 2013, Reuters 2015). In Aleppo, a month-long aerial bombing campaign carried out by the Russian-Syrian coalition not only committed war crimes against opposition-held areas but also shifted the military balance firmly in favor of the regime (Human Rights Watch 2016). Iran simultaneously deployed Revolutionary Guard forces, trained and financed militias, and embedded itself within Syria's security apparatus, there-

by entrenching sectarian networks within what remained of state institutions (Majidyar 2021). Meanwhile, Hizbullah provided military support throughout the civil war, deploying thousands of fighters, training pro-regime militias, and coordinating offensives alongside Syrian and Iranian forces (Mohanad Hage Ali 2019).

During conflict that involves foreign intervention, dictators must balance their domestic coalitions with the demands and incentives offered by foreign patrons. While the Asad regime was courting foreign sponsors, Bashar was also maintaining his autocratic rule. These competing interventions eroded Syria's sovereignty, as key decisions about the country's future, namely economic reconstruction, became contingent on external actors rather than domestic institutions. While the country was destitute, and with the limited amount of economic pie, the Asad regime was reportedly "selling the country" to Iranians and Russians through economic contracts in sectors such as energy, infrastructure, and security (Syrian Observatory for Human Rights 2023). They also corroded the regime's legitimacy: Asad's survival came to depend less on popular consent or functioning governance than on foreign sponsorship, leaving the state's administrative and infrastructural foundations severely weakened.

Foreign intervention not only eroded Syrian sovereignty but also weakened state capacity and domestic institutions. In exchange for political and military backing, allies such as Russia and Iran were granted privileged access to Syria's economy, creating a permissive business environment that extended deep into infrastructure and reconstruction projects (Observatory of Political and Economic Networks 2025). Economic contracts awarded to foreign companies spanned transpor-

tation, tourism, telecommunications, agriculture, education, finance, real estate, construction, and, most critically, the energy and infrastructure sectors (Syria Report 2022). Asad balanced between his allies by distributing contracts unevenly: while fewer Russian firms invested compared to Iranian ones, the value of Russian contracts was significantly higher.

A prominent example is the Russian company Stroytransgaz, which secured lucrative agreements with the Syrian Ministry of Oil to extract phosphate in eastern Palmyra, build two gas processing plants with a combined capacity of 9 million cubic meters per day, and construct the Syrian section of the Arab Gas Pipeline from the Jordanian border to the Al Rayan Gas Station near Homs (The Syrian Observer 2018; Syria Report 2022). Since 2018, the company has also managed Syria's main fertilizer plant and gained control over operations at the port of Tartous (Syria Report 2022). Although the extent of their current operations after the fall of the Asad regime remains unclear, their significant leverage over natural resources indicates how intertwined they are in the Syrian political economy (Observatory of Political and Economic Networks 2025). These arrangements demonstrate how Asad's regime traded slices of Syria's economy for foreign political and military support, creating a quid pro quo system of aid-for-access that propped up his rule in the short term but hollowed out state sovereignty and institutional capacity.

In autocracies, such external rents operate as unearned income that allows rulers to sustain patronage networks and extend their tenure without strengthening state institutions (Ahmed 2012). Authoritarian governments are compelled to balance internal coalitions with external patrons in order to safeguard

regime stability. However, when an autocrat becomes dependent on foreign backers for survival, they often prioritize redistributing resources and granting economic access to those external patrons instead of maintaining a balanced domestic coalition. This tradeoff sacrifices long-term regime strength for short-term regime survival, hollowing out state institutions in the process. Bashar al-Asad's Syria illustrates this dynamic vividly: to preserve his rule, Asad restructured socioeconomic policies and state contracts to reward foreign allies—particularly Russia and Iran—over domestic constituencies, gradually weakening the state's administrative and economic foundations.

This foreign-dependent model left the regime brittle, functioning more as a façade propped up by external sponsorship than as a cohesive political order; ultimately, it collapsed like a house of cards. Yet foreign involvement was not limited to Asad's allies; opposition factions also received extensive backing from Gulf states and Türkiye, while U.S. engagement shifted over time—from President Obama's "red line" rhetoric on chemical weapons to a later focus on supporting the Syrian Democratic Forces (SDF) against ISIS. The new Sharaa government must contend with the historical persistence and institutional legacies of Asad's rule—and it would do well to draw lessons from how foreign dependence hollowed out its predecessor.

Avoiding Too Many Cooks in the Kitchen: Governance Today

The transitional government has attracted a surge of foreign investment pledges aimed at accelerating reconstruction and stabilizing Syria's devastated economy. These deals could jump-start recovery, especially as the United States and European Union have been lifting

most sanctions, reopening access to global banking, technology, and reconstruction materials (U.S. Department of State 2025, Council of the European Union 2025). Saudi Arabia has positioned itself as a central backer. In July 2025, it announced \$6.4 billion in planned investments, including \$2.93 billion for real estate and infrastructure and about \$1.07 billion for telecommunications and IT (Reuters 2025a). Syria also signed 44 investment agreements with Saudi Arabia worth nearly \$6 billion, spanning energy, banking, and manufacturing, including a major cement plant in Adra Industrial City (Al-Monitor 2025, Reuters 2025e).

Together, these investment flows and the lifting of sanctions are poised to reshape the foreign influence landscape in Syria, shifting leverage away from wartime patrons like Russia and Iran toward Gulf states and Western actors seeking to anchor their role in the country's reconstruction. Yet without strong institutional safeguards, this influx risks creating a 'too many cooks in the kitchen' scenario, where fragmented external agendas undermine coherent governance and delay genuine state-building.

Additionally, the al-Sharaa government concluded a broader \$14 billion package of Gulf-led deals, notably including a \$4 billion expansion of Damascus International Airport by Qatar's UCC Holding and the construction of tens of thousands of new housing units (Reuters 2025b, Al-Jazeera 2025). Qatar has also pledged to rebuild Syria's national electrical grid, committing several billion dollars to overhaul generation plants, transmission lines, and smart-grid infrastructure, aiming to stabilize power delivery nationwide (Reuters 2025c). Azerbaijan has entered the reconstruction arena as well, signing a long-term oil export and refinery modernization

deal projected to revitalize Syria's coastal refineries and guarantee stable fuel supplies for the domestic market (Middle East Monitor 2025). Meanwhile, Russia has reasserted its stake, dispatching a high-level delegation in September 2025 to discuss aid and the restoration of Syria's energy sector (Reuters 2025d).

While these pledges signal renewed diplomatic openings and potential for post-conflict reconstruction, they also carry familiar risks from political science research on intervention and democratization. Aid and external support can create powerful distortions in governance priorities. In many low- and middle-income states, large foreign inflows expand government spending while simultaneously eroding domestic revenue generation, leaving states fiscally dependent on external actors rather than their own societies (Remmer 2004). This dynamic often weakens state capacity and accountability.

Moreover, foreign aid has been shown to function as a "resource curse," in some cases proving even more corrosive to democratization and regime type than natural resource rents (Djankov, Montalvo, and Reynal-Querol 2008). By substituting international backing for the need to manage domestic elite coalitions, external support can unravel existing power-sharing arrangements and centralize authority in brittle, personalized networks (Boix and Svulik 2013). The dilemma of reconstruction is precisely this: while foreign capital is indispensable to accelerate recovery, dependence on it risks discouraging the pursuit of genuine power-sharing with local actors and deepening reliance on external patrons. Avoiding this trap requires channeling resources through accountable domestic institutions and designing reconstruction in ways that strengthen state legitimacy rather

than elite patronage.

Transparent public auction systems for reconstruction contracts, redistribution of investment toward marginalized regions such as Kurdish and Druze areas, and the cultivation of civil society can ensure that foreign inflows contribute to inclusive governance rather than perpetuate fragility. The literature also shows that external assistance can catalyze democratic openings only when resources are channeled through accountable domestic institutions, rather than informal patronage networks (Gleditsch, Christiansen, and Hegre 2007; Doyle and Sambanis 2006). Otherwise, external funding tends to hollow out governance, entrench elite capture, and undermine legitimacy (Mansfield and Snyder 2005; Bueno de Mesquita and Downs 2006).

To avoid repeating this pattern, the al-Sharaa government must focus on investing in its people and political processes. A central challenge is building strong institutions without ceding sovereignty to external policy agendas. When governments allow foreign investments to be tied to specific individuals or political patrons rather than institutional frameworks, donors become more invested in personal relationships and patronage networks than in the institutions themselves—undermining the very structures that are supposed to carry Syria forward. This personalization of governance creates fragility, as political change can collapse entire networks of funding and administration. There is a fine line between short-term stability and long-term governance, prosperity, and sustainability. Reconstruction contracts must pass through state institutions using a transparent public auction system, especially given the current opacity surrounding contract allocation. Transparency would help rebuild legitimacy by showing that the state serves the

public rather than private elites. A circular investment strategy that redistributes resources to marginalized Kurdish and Druze regions would further foster inclusion, demonstrating that state institutions invest in all Syrians—and thereby anchoring legitimacy in equitable development.

Conclusion

As Syria now tentatively enters a transitional phase, this legacy presents both a warning and an opportunity. Rather than stabilizing regimes, foreign support can generate profound internal instability by creating a quid pro quo dynamic that distorts governance priorities. To prevent renewed fragmentation, the emergent government must pursue stronger centralization and state capacity with the buy-in of both majority and minority communities, yet in ways that safeguard sovereignty rather than substitute for it. International actors can contribute by coordinating reconstruction assistance that rebuilds infrastructure and public administration without imposing political designs, while simultaneously fostering civil society to cultivate a domestic civic political culture capable of sustaining participatory governance. This agenda requires reckoning with the persistent pull of foreign intervention and the reality that Syria's political systems and institutions remain fragile, underdeveloped, and vulnerable to capture—demanding careful state-building that prioritizes institutional resilience over external dependency.

Syria's transition offers a rare chance to rebuild a unified, sovereign state. Centralizing authority is necessary to stabilize governance, but it must be paired with safeguards for sovereignty, institutional transparency, and civil inclusion. The lifting of Western sanctions provides economic oxygen, but without

careful management, it could also invite competing foreign agendas. The new government must avoid becoming another vessel for outside powers and instead channel international support into domestic institutions, civic culture, and resilient economic governance—ensuring that Syria's future is built by Syrians, not bartered away to foreign patrons. ♦

References

- Action on Armed Violence. 2024. *The Foreign Forces in Syria's Conflict: A Brief Explainer*. London: AOAV.
- Ahmed, Faisal Z. 2012. "The Perils of Unearned Foreign Income: Aid, Remittances, and Government Survival." *American Political Science Review* 106(1): 146–165.
- Al-Monitor. 2025. "Saudi Business Delegation Arrives in Syria, Deals Worth \$4–6 Billion Seen." *Al-Monitor*, July 25, 2025.
- Allison, Roy. 2013. "Russia and Syria: Explaining Alignment with a Regime in Crisis." *International Affairs* 89(4): 795–823.
- Boix, Carles, and Milan Svobik. 2013. "The Foundations of Limited Authoritarian Government: Institutions, Commitment, and Power-Sharing in Dictatorships." *Journal of Politics* 75(2): 300–316.
- Bueno de Mesquita, Bruce, and George Downs. 2006. "Intervention and Democracy." *International Organization* 60(3): 627–649.
- Council of the European Union. 2025. "Syria: EU Adopts Legal Acts to Lift Economic Sanctions on Syria, Enacting Recent Political Agreement." *Press Release*, May 28, 2025.

“Damascus Signs New Contract With Russian Company to Extract Phosphate.” 2018. *The Syrian Observer*, March 26, 2018.

Djankov, Simeon, José G. Montalvo, and Marta Reynal-Querol. 2008. “The Curse of Aid.” *Journal of Economic Growth* 13: 169–194.

Doyle, Michael W., and Nicholas Sambanis. 2006. *Making War and Building Peace: United Nations Peace Operations*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.

Gleditsch, Kristian S., Lene Christiansen, and Håvard Hegre. 2007. “Democratic Jihad? Military Intervention and Democracy.” *European Journal of International Relations* 13(1): 129–152.

Human Rights Watch. 2016. “Russia/Syria: War Crimes in Month of Bombing Aleppo.” Human Rights Watch, December 1, 2016. Accessed [date you accessed].

Majidiyar, Ahmad. 2021. “Iran Recruits and Trains Large Numbers of Afghan and Pakistani Shiites.” *Middle East Institute*, April 15, 2021.

Mansfield, Edward D., and Jack Snyder. 2005. *Electing to Fight: Why Emerging Democracies Go to War*. Cambridge: MIT Press.

Middle East Monitor. 2025. “Azerbaijan’s State Oil Company Signs Gas Supply MoU with Syria.” *Middle East Monitor*, July 12, 2025.

Mohanad Hage Ali. 2019. “Power Points Defining the Syria-Hizbullah Relationship.” *Carnegie Endowment for International Peace*, March 29, 2019.

Observatory of Political and Economic Networks. 2025. “Iran’s Economic Involvement in Syria and Its Implications (2011–2024).” *OpenSyr*.

Observatory of Political and Economic Networks. 2025. “Russia’s Economic Footprint in Syria and the Implications of Asad’s Downfall.” *OpenSyr*.

Phillips, C. 2020. *The Battle for Syria: International Rivalry in the New Middle East*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.

Remmer, Karen L. 2004. “Does Foreign Aid Promote the Expansion of Government?” *American Journal of Political Science* 48(1): 77–92.

Reuters. 2015. “Asad: Russia Is Supplying Weapons to Syria under Contracts Finalized since the Conflict Began.” *Reuters*, May 30, 2015.

Reuters. 2025a. “Saudi Arabia Announces \$6.4 Billion Syria Investments.” *Reuters*, July 24, 2025.

Reuters. 2025b. “Syria Signs \$7 Billion Power Deal with Qatar’s UCC Holding-led Consortium.” *Reuters*, May 29, 2025.

Reuters. 2025c. “For Syria, Qatar’s \$7 Billion Power Plan Hinges on Fixing Its Grid.” *Reuters*, June 2, 2025.

Reuters. 2025d. “Russia Sends High-Level Team to Syria to Discuss Aid, Energy.” *Reuters*, September 9, 2025.

Reuters. 2025e. “Saudi Business Delegation Arrives in Syria; Deals Worth \$4 Billion to \$6 Billion Seen Being Signed.” *Reuters*, July 23, 2025.

Syria Report. 2022. “Factsheet: Syria-Russia Economic Relations.” *Syria Report*, February 22, 2022.

“Stroytransgaz.” 2022. Syria Report.

Syrian Observatory for Human Rights. 2023.

“‘Asad Sold Syria’ | Sentences Written on Walls Against the Syrian Regime in Al-Suwaydaa.” Syrian Observatory for Human Rights, January 17, 2023.

U.S. Department of State. 2025. “Termination of Syria Sanctions.” Office of the Spokesperson, June 30, 2025.

Power, Control, and State (De)Formation under Hayat Tahrir al-Sham

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Salam Said is a Syrian academic and economist with expertise in Arab economies and the political economy of Syria, particularly post-war reconstruction. Said has published various academic and policy papers focusing on political economy and geopolitical analysis in Syria.

Syria is currently undergoing a historic transition: a crucial state (re)formation after fourteen years of war that destroyed a large part of the Syrian economy and displaced over half of the population. Moreover, the takeover of Damascus by Hayat Tahrir al-Sham (HTS) does not represent a transition from a repressive military dictatorship to a democratic state grounded in citizenship and the rule of law. Rather, it reflects the reproduction of coercive and unjust power structures that have dominated Syria for the past fifty years, with only a redistribution of roles among those in power and between victims and perpetrators, without substantive transformation of the underlying political order.

This paper analyzes the current transitional leadership under Ahmed al-Sharaa, rebel leader of HTS, based on Michael Mann's concepts of "infrastructural" and "despotic" state sources of power. Infrastructural power, grounded in institutional cooperation with society and efficient provision of services, contrasts with despotic power, which relies on coercion and violence by the ruling elite to control society. While both forms often coexist, an overreliance on despotic power increases the risk of state failure, whereas strengthening infrastructural power enhances state resilience (Mann 1984).

The Syrian state under HTS's transitional leadership is relying heavily on violence to assert control over its territories. At this critical juncture of state reshaping—requiring exceptional capacity to navigate internal and geopolitical challenges—the state has failed to build institutions, gain public trust, or operate as more than a militia.

Consolidation of Power

By reclaiming power through "revolutionary legitimacy" in February 2025 (Ziade 2025) and later through "transitional legitimacy," based on a controversial constitutional declaration that granted the president virtually unlimited authorities (HRW 2025), transitional president al-Sharaa has centralized and concentrated power in unprecedented ways—holding multiple key posts simultaneously, including President, quasi-Prime Minister, head of the armed forces, chair of the Supreme Judicial Council, head of the Sovereign Wealth Fund, and chair of the National Development Fund. In addition to holding both executive and judicial authorities, he is poised to dominate parliamentary decision-making by directly appointing 30% of its members. At all state levels, appointments are made by al-Sharaa's inner circle, echoing the exclusionary practices of the Asad era. Genuine participa-

tion and bottom-up governance are absent (Haid 2025).

Fragile state institutions have been further weakened and infiltrated by HTS members since December 2024. Experts working closely with the transitional government report highly centralized decision-making, marked by a lack of transparency and accountability. Ministers unaffiliated with HTS hold little genuine authority, as members in less visible roles—reporting directly to al-Sharaa’s inner circle—dictate key decisions. They report the creation of “parallel bodies” led by HTS that routinely override state institutions (personal conversation 2025a).

HTS consolidates power over the economy through clientelism and the placement of relatives in key positions.¹ This reproduces political-economic patterns of inequality and cronyism seen under Asad, as the business network around al-Sharaa relocated from Idlib to Damascus, and began to receive privileges in looting public resources and dominating the market. Sham Bank, for instance, a private bank established by HTS in 2018 in Idlib, holds now a privileged market share position and is contracted to handle public salaries. It appears to operate as a parallel “Central Bank.”²

The neoliberal policies adopted by HTS have reinforced this “state capture” through privatization, outsourcing of basic services, and opaque investment agreements with interna-

tional firms. A free market for HTS does not necessarily mean competition; rather, it often means that business companies owned by the elite enjoy monopolies and operate outside the rule of law (Al-Khatib 2024). To date, there is no information on how state assets—particularly properties of the Ministry of Defense and the Ministry of Awqaf—are managed.

HTS fighters, who are meanwhile employees of the interior and defense ministries, receive salaries three to four times higher than those of ordinary civil servants, along with housing and other benefits.³ These benefits can secure loyalty to the leadership and are likely to result in the accumulation of wealth within HTS circles. Recruitment into the privileged armed forces is highly selective and follows strict ideological criteria. According to an applicant, “You have to be one of them,” meaning aligned with HTS ideology (Personal conversation 2025b).

Beyond economic control, HTS increasingly relies on ideology to consolidate dominance by promoting its interpretation of Islam and national identity. Military training embeds ideological instruction that excludes Syrians with differing beliefs, while religious institutions such as the Ministry of Awqaf and the High Islamic Council have seen personnel replaced to align with this agenda. Although the government officially advocates a moderate religious discourse, HTS propaganda reinforces its own narrative by tolerating hate

1 The president’s brothers hold key positions, including Chairman of the Investment Authority and Secretary-General to the Presidency, while his brother-in-law serves as Secretary of the new Syrian Central Bank (Enab Baladi 2025a).

2 See e.g. Al Modon (2025).

3 There is no official publication regarding the salaries of HTS fighters. However, in personal conversations with two applicants for the armed Forces in February in Damascus, they mentioned that the salary would be \$125. They also stated that HTS fighters earn between \$200 and \$400 per month, depending on rank. Employees in the public sector earn between \$20 and \$120. The latter is a salary for professor at the university. (Eqtsad. 2025 and The Arab Weekly 2025)

speech and sectarian mobilization against moderate Islam and other faiths—most evident during the coastal massacres in March and in as-Sweida in July (Enab Baladi 2025b, STJ 2025).

The de facto power consolidation contradicts the promises conveyed by al-Sharaa in his speeches regarding participation, inclusivity, and justice. In particular, women—who were encouraged by the president’s “inclusive and gender-sensitive” first speech—are deeply disappointed by the limited women’s representation in key positions and the shrinking public spaces for women (Hassan 2025, Asad 2025). This frustration is shared by political parties, journalists, and activists, who face persistent challenges in the absence of clear regulation of their work, reviving memories of the climate of fear that prevailed under the previous regime (Hamou 2025).

Despotic Power

The transitional leadership under al-Sharaa has shown a profound inability to formulate or implement state policies, undermining the infrastructural power of the state. For instance, committees on transitional justice and reconstruction exist but have produced no tangible outcomes. No public prosecutions for crimes against humanity have been pursued, and no national plan addresses socioeconomic challenges such as poverty, unemployment, or refugee repatriation. Service provision as a key mechanism for strengthening state-society trust is entirely absent, and the promised new social contract has not been negotiated. International pledges of hundreds of millions of dollars in investment remain unfulfilled, recalling Asad’s reconstruction rhetoric since 2018. Given Syria’s persistent political instability and incapacity to repair fundamental infrastructure, such

investment contracts are unlikely to materialize.

These patterns also recall HTS’s governance in Idlib during the war, where the group pursued a neoliberal model in which service provision was framed as charity rather than as a right. This approach left war-torn communities to cope with essential needs such as healthcare, water, and electricity largely through INGO support, while state resources are diverted toward administration and military operations (Al-Zaraee and Shaar 2021). Now, with the reduction and elimination of humanitarian aid from global North countries, INGO support may not even be forthcoming.

The leadership in Damascus relies heavily on a despotic conception of the state, deriving power primarily from coercion and centralization. To assert control over Syrian territories, HTS employs a militarized approach, disregarding diplomacy or genuine dialogue. Military operations on the coast, in the Damascus suburbs, and in as-Sweida reveal that official forces often function as militias driven by ideological zeal rather than disciplined armies. According to the UN Commission of Inquiry on Syria, these forces have committed crimes and human rights violations systematically (*OHCHR 2025*), including the brutal killing of civilians and looting of property, reflecting ideological motives. The human toll of these operations together exceeded 3,500 killed and hundreds of thousands displaced since March 2025 (see reports of SOHR 2025). This approach was adopted by the previous regime in 2011 and proved ineffective in maintaining power or achieving stability.

HTS employs sectarianism and social polarization to consolidate power and neutralize

rivals through loyalty-building. Sectarianism, institutionalized in Syria during the Ottoman and French colonial periods to weaken national resistance, was also extensively used by the Asad regime (Kastrinou 2016). This approach empowers religious, ethnic, and tribal leaders to represent their communities more than political leaders who embody common political values across religions and ethnicities.

Geopolitical actors, including Israel and Turkey, have exploited these divisions to strengthen their negotiating leverage within Syria. Such interventions threaten not only national integrity, which HTS claims to uphold, but also social cohesion and a shared Syrian identity. Calls for decentralization in northeastern Syria and in as-Sweida reflect the consequences of these policies (Kastrinou and Said 2025). Consequently, the central leadership in Damascus risks losing its legitimacy as a representative of all Syrians, further exposing state dysfunction and undermining public acceptance of coercive authority.

Conclusion

HTS has relied on coercion, sectarian and gender exclusion, and systemic violence instead of dialogue, trust, and institution-building. By prioritizing despotic power over infrastructural power—focusing on security and coercion while failing to provide essential services or build functional institutions—this transitional leadership undermines social cohesion and threatens Syria's stability. The deliberate hollowing out and predation of state institutions and targeting of populations with differing values or beliefs demonstrates a systematic, rather than individual, approach to control, exemplifying the deformation of the state. ♦

References

- Al-Zaraee, Nisreen, and Shaar, Karam. 2021. *The Economics of Hayat Tahrir al-Sham*. *Middle East Institute*, June 21.
- Asad, Rula. 2025 "Ignored Voices: Women and the Media in Syria's New Era." *International Media Support*, March 10.
- Eqtsad. 2025. "Salaries of Fighters in Syria's Militias: Disparity Between Different Groups." *Eqtsad*, May 31.
- Enab Baladi. 2025b. "Syrian Ministry of Awqaf Calls for Adherence to Moderate Religious Discourse." *Enab Baladi*, May 26.
- Haid, Haid. 2025. "Where Does Syria's Transition Stand?" *Arab Reform Initiative*, April 24.
- Hassan, Maha. 2025. "From Assad to al-Sharaa: Syrian Women Are Still Being Repressed." *The New Arab*, August 4.
- Hamou, Ammar. 2025. "Yasser al-Aiti: 'A Syria without political parties will revert to tyranny.'" *Syria Direct*, January 21.
- Kesah, Mohammad. "Khās 'al-mudun': Tawsi'a bank shām 'ala hisāb sharakat al-sirāfa." *Al-Modon*. 2 June 2025.
- Kastrinou, A. Maria. 2016. *Power, Sect, and State in Syria: The Politics of Marriage and Identity Amongst the Druze*. London: I.B. Tauris.
- Kastrinou, Maria, and Salam Said. 2025. "Not a Local Conflict, but Geopolitics in Disguise." *Qantara.de*, July 28.

Mann, Michael. 1984. "The Autonomous Power of the State: Its Origins, Mechanisms and Results." *European Journal of Sociology / Archives Européennes de Sociologie* 25 (2): 185–213.

Syrian Observatory for Human Rights (SOHR). 2025. Syrian Observatory for Human Rights. Accessed August 17, 2025.

Syrians for Truth and Justice (STJ). 2025. *Syria: The Role of Hate Speech in the Massacres that Took Place in the Coastal Region in March 2025*. Syrians for Truth and Justice, May 26.

The Arab Weekly 2025, A. "Syria Announces Increase in Pensions and Public Sector Wages." *The Arab Weekly*, August 17.

United Nations Human Rights Office. "UN Syria Commission Finds March Coastal Violence Was Widespread and Systematic." *OHCHR*, August 14, 2025.

Ziadeh, Radwan. 2025. "Revolutionary Legitimacy in Syria: Sharaa as President." *Arab Center Washington DC*, February 2025.

Personal Conversations

- Personal conversation with two applicants to the Ministry of Defense, Damascus, Feb. 2025.
- Multiple conversations with consultants working with the current government, in person and via Zoom, between February and August 2025.

No Justice, No Peace? A Challenge for Syria

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Introduction

In 2011, Syria's nonviolent movement was unsuccessful in its attempt to peacefully overthrow the government. Violent repression of the movement escalated into a civil war between the government and rebel groups. Now, more than a decade after the uprising began, Syria's rebels join the ranks of the few violent movements that have succeeded in toppling a government since 2010. The country's recovery will be more challenging than it would have been following peaceful civil resistance (Chenoweth 2020).

Societies affected by killing, wounding, and death continue to suffer the physiological and psychosocial effects after conflict ends (Collier et al. 2008), with families and communities broken up and violence becoming a common response to injustice. Production, labour, transport, communication, and infrastructures need rebuilding, and this puts economies under pressure, causing life expectancy to drop during transitions out of violent resistance, more than out of non-violence (Stoddard 2013). Regimes that fall due to violent civil resistance also develop higher levels of autocracy than those that fall through peaceful resistance (Tarrow 2007).

In Syria today, there are signs that a demo-

cratic veneer is being used to cover autocratic consolidation by the al-Sharaa government in Syria, making rights groups “wary” (MacDonald 2025). The interim electoral system has been described as based on both “selection and election,” with interim President al-Sharaa directly appointing one-third of parliament and province-level electoral bodies formed by the government tasked with selecting the remaining two-thirds. Structures of power are also being centralized around al-Sharaa and his brothers, while Hayat Tahrir al-Sham (HTS) loyalists hold key ministries, including defense, foreign affairs, and interior (Abdulrahim 2025).

The presence of very limited minority group members and just one woman in the interim cabinet suggests inclusion is a low priority. This curt nod to religious, ethnic, and gender representation in the cabinet may appease international observers while Syria trends toward authoritarianism (ETANA 2025). In fact, analysts warn that HTS is consolidating power by “gaining external recognition and legitimation to foster its domination within the country” (Daher 2025) — a task helped by democratic signaling.

When process-based inclusion is lacking — that is, when minority and citizen voices are not let into decision-making — there is a risk that outcomes, such as social welfare, educ-

ation, health, and economic growth, as well as justice and accountability, will be distributed to preferred groups. Additionally, any distributions of outcomes along religious or ethnic lines have the potential to deepen divides already threatening the stability of Syria's transition, and reminiscent of Ba'athist policies which exploited kin and clientelist networks (Neep 2025; Hinnebusch 2021).

Sectarian violence has been escalating in the last six months. In June 2025, the Mar Elias Church in Damascus was attacked, killing 25 people and injuring 63, in the first attack in Damascus since the overthrow of Assad and possibly the work of the Islamic State (IS), or Saraya Ansar al-Sunnah, a splinter group of HTS that may have ties to IS (Zelin 2025b). In Sweida, deadly clashes between Bedouin tribes and the Druze minority broke out in July, with government-affiliated forces soon implicated in the March 6th massacre of hundreds of 'Alawite civilians on the Syrian coast (Zelin 2025a). The Syrian Network for Human Rights recorded 2818 civilians killed across the country in the first half of 2025 (SNHR 2025a).

The SNHR has called on the government to “regulate the use of force” and work toward accountability and community trust in justice institutions through “open, independent, and transparent investigations into all reported violations, including extrajudicial killings, abductions, arbitrary detention, and degrading treatment” (SNHR 2025b).

Syria's transition is occurring while the global order is trending toward foreign aid reductions, military spending, protection, and autocratization. Dominant neo-liberal democratic ideals underpinning foreign policymaking are weak. Yet, global interest in a democratic transition in Syria remains high

because of its geostrategic position in the MENA region and shifts in alliances triggered by the regime's fall, as well as some recognition of what is owed to Syrians who rose up and fought to topple a brutal dictatorship. How will these tensions be resolved?

A Democratic Future?

Democratization in conflict-affected settings can lead to the recurrence of civil war. Theoretically, democracy offers alternatives to violence as a mechanism for resolving disputes and addressing sources of conflict through democratized resource and benefit sharing (Hegre 2014). In practice, elections often generate new violence in countries recovering from civil war (Höglund et al. 2009), with long-term stability more likely in high-income, older, consolidated democracies: “democratic strategies for maintaining order may be more costly than the autocratic strategies” (Hegre 2014, 167).

Still, scholars know that strong institutions that are representative of the population can also help reduce fear (Mattes and Savun 2009), and support groups in making more credible and transparent commitments (Bara et al. 2021; Suhrke and Berdal 2013). They can make it harder for grievances to inspire violence (Boyle 2014; Steenkamp 2014). Where women are represented in post-war institutions, peace may be prolonged (Shair-Rosenfield and Wood 2017). Strong law enforcement institutions make engaging in violence—including non-political crime—more costly (Gartner and Kennedy 2018).

So, what should scholars and analysts say about the democratic future of Syria? We must understand and point to parallel imperatives to champion accountability and justice. Any transition to democracy must be gradual

(Carothers 2007), locally driven, and coupled with efforts to strengthen institutions and foster peace (Mross 2019).

Questions about Syria's future regime type and power structures are important, and matter to the press, the public, and, most importantly, Syrians. But, as scholars of the Middle East, it is crucial that we continue to champion Syrian human rights, civil society, community, and diaspora actors' calls for justice and accountability. In this moment of foreign aid and democratic retrenchment, relying on and supporting local action is more important than ever.

Justice and Accountability

Article 49 of the Syrian Constitutional Declaration specifies, "A transitional justice commission shall be established, adopting effective, victim-centered mechanisms to determine accountability mechanisms, the right to know the truth, and justice for victims and survivors, in addition to honoring martyrs." (Presidency of the Syrian Arab Republic Declaration 2025, 14). National Commissions for Transitional Justice and for the Missing were established by presidential decree in May and are meant to produce accountability and justice for past crimes, and to govern future conduct of the Syrian state.

The founder of the civil society group Syrian Network for Human Rights has, however, argued that the establishment of these bodies by presidential decree and not through a legislative council may make it harder to center Syrian national ownership, protect independence from the executive and the ministry of justice, and better guarantee funding (Abdulghany 2025). He wrote of the need for these Commissions to hold a range of investigative powers: "This is particularly important given

the priority of accessing documents from security branches, prisons, hospitals, and courts, which addresses the challenge of accessing archives that typically arises in contexts where previous authorities have deliberately concealed or destroyed official records" (*Ibid.*).

The International Center for Transitional Justice highlighted the need for inquiries to be grounded in affected communities, coordinate with civil society actors and international institutions, and for the Commissions to be inclusive in their engagement and outreach (ICTJ 2025). Meanwhile, survivor-led accountability movements that have formed throughout the last decade require pathways to inclusion (Bernath 2025), and there is a need to protect the independence and documentation of atrocity crimes created by the Syrian White Helmets—a challenge given the organization voted overwhelmingly to be integrated into the new government.

These are just a few of the pressing justice and accountability challenges in Syria.

Conclusion

In the absence of justice, there will be no peace. Principles of truth, justice, and accountability, and the laws and norms that underpin them, are under threat globally. Yet, scholars interested in supporting the calls of Syrians can build and share knowledge about how representation, accountability, justice, and peace can be achieved in Syria, even while the globe trends toward impunity. ♦

References

Abdulrahim, Raja. 2025. "As Syria Tries to Move Away From Dictatorship, Signs of Authoritarianism Linger." *The New York Times*.

- Bara, Corinne, Annekatriin Deglow, and Sebastian Van Baalen. 2021. "Civil War Recurrence and Postwar Violence: Toward an Integrated Research Agenda." *European Journal of International Relations* 27 (3): 913–35.
- Bernath, Julie. 2025. "Mobilizing for Syria's Disappeared: Survivor-Led Movements, Emotions, and Transitional Justice." *Journal of Human Rights Practice* 17 (2): huaf006.
- Boyle, Michael J. 2014. *Violence after War: Explaining Instability in Post-Conflict States*. JHU Press.
- Carothers, Thomas. 2007. "How Democracies Emerge: The 'Sequencing' Fallacy." *Journal of Democracy* 18 (1): 12–27.
- Chenoweth, Erica. 2020. "The Future of Non-violent Resistance." *Journal of Democracy* 31 (3): 69–84.
- Collier, Paul, Anke Hoeffler, and Måns Söderbom. 2008. "Post-Conflict Risks." *Journal of Peace Research* 45 (4): 461–78.
- Daher, Joseph. 2025. "HTS' Strategy to Consolidate Its Power in Syria." *Syria Untold*.
- ETANA. 2025. "BRIEF: Syria's Interim Cabinet—between Inclusion & Power Consolidation." *ETANA*.
- Gartner, Rosemary, and Liam Kennedy. 2018. "War and Postwar Violence." *Crime and Justice* 47 (1): 1–67.
- Hegre, Håvard. 2014. "Democracy and Armed Conflict." *Journal of Peace Research* 51 (2): 159–72.
- Hinnebusch, Raymond A. 2021. *Authoritarian Power and State Formation in Ba'athist Syria: Army, Party, and Peasant*. Routledge.
- Höglund, Kristine, Anna K Jarstad, and Mimmi Söderberg Kovacs. 2009. "The Predicament of Elections in War-Torn Societies." *Democratization* 16 (3): 530–57.
- ICTJ. 2025. ICTJ Welcomes Establishment of Syria's New National Commissions for Transitional Justice and the Missing.
- MacDonald, Alex. 2025. "Syrian Democracy Campaigners Wary of Upcoming 'selected' Elections." *Middle East Eye*.
- Mattes, Michaela, and Burcu Savun. 2009. "Fostering Peace after Civil War: Commitment Problems and Agreement Design." *International Studies Quarterly* 53 (3): 737–59.
- Mross, Karina. 2019. "First Peace, Then Democracy? Evaluating Strategies of International Support at Critical Junctures after Civil War." *International Peacekeeping* 26 (2): 190–215.
- Neep, Daniel. 2025. "Rebuilding the State in Post-Assad Syria." *Journal of Democracy* 36 (2): 68–77.
- Presidency of the Syrian Arab Republic Declaration. 2025. *Constitutional Declaration of the Syrian Arab Republic*. Government.
- Shair-Rosenfield, Sarah, and Reed M Wood. 2017. "Governing Well after War: How Improving Female Representation Prolongs Post-Conflict Peace." *The Journal of Politics* 79 (3): 995–1009.

SNHR. 2025a. The Death of 140 Civilians Including 10 Children and 15 Women, and One Death Due to Torture Recorded in June 2025. Monthly Report for Victims of Extrajudicial Killing in Syria. Syrian Network for Human Rights.

SNHR. 2025b. Update of Latest Toll: At Least 814 Syrians Have Been Killed and More than 903 Others Injured in Suwayda Governorate since July 13. Syrian Network for Human Rights.

Steenkamp, Christina. 2014. *Violent Societies: Networks of Violence in Civil War and Peace*. Springer.

Stoddard, Judith. 2013. "How Do Major, Violent and Nonviolent Opposition Campaigns, Impact Predicted Life Expectancy at Birth?" *Stability: International Journal of Security and Development* 2 (2): 37–37.

Suhrke, Astri, and Mats Berdal. 2013. *The Peace in between: Post-War Violence and Peacebuilding*. Routledge.

Tarrow, Sidney. 2007. "Inside Insurgencies: Politics and Violence in an Age of Civil War." *Perspectives on Politics* 5 (3): 587–600.

Zelin, Aaron. 2025a. "Syria's Transitional Honeymoon Is Over After Massacres and Disinformation." The Washington Institute for Near East Policy.

Zelin, Aaron. 2025b. "The Damascus Church Attack: Who Is Saraya Ansar al-Sunnah?" The Washington Institute for Near East Policy.

Counting Return and Understanding Transition: Syrian Refugee and IDP Movements

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In the aftermath of more than a decade of conflict, the question of return looms large in Syria's future. "Refugee return" is often invoked as a marker of stability and a step toward national recovery. Yet the reality is far more complicated. Returns are partial, often temporary, and deeply entangled with the processes of post-conflict reconstruction. They are rarely a linear "end state" but part of a dynamic mobility cycle that can include multiple departures before settlement becomes sustainable. Moreover, how we count returns and what those numbers reveal or conceal are very important.

Despite the appearance of a more settled political map, Syria still remains a country in motion. Refugees cross borders back into Syria, sometimes only to leave again; internally displaced persons (IDPs) shuttle between camps, informal settlements, and damaged home communities; and local flare-ups of violence continue to disrupt return plans. These movements resist the linear narrative of "going home" and instead reflect a churn of return and remigration that will likely define Syria's "transition" for years to come. Studies on circular and stepwise migration show that returns are likely to be followed by remigra-

tion, and such patterns are neither unique to Syria nor inherently short-lived—they often reflect deliberate household strategies to manage risk (de Haas, 2010; Sahin-Mencutek, 2023). In the Syrian case, these "test returns" and staggered movements are a rational adaptation to volatile conditions. The politics of return are, therefore, inseparable from the politics of transition. How return is measured, represented, and acted upon can also shape not just humanitarian planning but also Syria's contested postwar order.

The Measurement Challenge

Measuring return migration is never straightforward, even in peacetime. As Oliver Bakewell (1999) and Richard Black (2002) argue, migration statistics are socially and politically constructed; they reflect not only movements but also the bureaucratic and political systems that record them. In recent years, datafication has become a core feature of migration governance. Despite the contentious negotiations over the Global Compact for Migration (GCM) in 2017–2018, the quantification of migration through digital technologies garnered widespread support from states, many of which have built digi-

tized systems of data collection, analysis, and dissemination. Yet states' reporting rarely aligns. In the 1970s, for example, German data on Italian repatriation exceeded Italy's own statistics on return from Germany by a factor of two, as Russell King (1993) notes. In Poland in the 1990s, substantial returns went uncounted because many emigrants in the 1980s had never registered as emigrants (Koser, 2016). These cases underscore a broader point: definitions of "return migration" and the methods used to count it vary widely—even within a single country, sometimes across different agencies (de Haas, Castles, & Miller, 2020).

Syria exemplifies these challenges. Some refugees re-enter without passing through official crossing points or notifying host-country authorities; others undertake short-term or circular returns that may not be captured at all. The result is a statistical picture that is necessarily incomplete. A further conceptual distinction is critical: flows versus stocks. Flow data captures how many people return over a specific period (weekly, monthly, annually), while stock data reflects the total size of the returned population at a point in time. Flows reveal short-term dynamics and policy effects; stocks indicate the cumulative scale of reintegration challenges. Conflating the two risks obscuring the patterns that matter most for understanding the evolving return landscape in a given context. As I discuss in the following paragraphs, the UN Refugee Agency (UNHCR)'s governorate-level data on Syrian refugee returns demonstrate why this distinction matters. Short-term dips in flows often track local fighting, while gradual increases in stocks signal more sustained—if still fragile—settlement.

What the Numbers Tell Us

While return numbers are always contested, UNHCR provides the most systematic and widely used data available. According to its Operational Data Portal, between 2016 and October 2024, approximately 435,395 Syrian refugees were recorded as having returned to the country, most to opposition-controlled areas. After the fall of the Assad regime, recorded returns surged, with UNHCR reporting 746,360 people—a sharp increase in a relatively short period. Figure 1 visualizes the return statistics across Syria's fourteen governorates after the fall of the regime, between 8 December 2024 and 31 July 2025, and Figure 2 provides the overall return statistics since 2016. Figure 1 reveals the uneven geography of these returns.

Densely populated areas and regions such as Aleppo, Damascus, Idlib, and Rural Damascus account for the largest shares, with Aleppo alone recording over 145,499 returns. Aleppo's high figures may also reflect its role as one of the main origins of Syrian refugees, particularly to Turkey, which hosts the largest number of Syrians overall. By contrast, smaller or more contested governorates such as as-Sweida, Quneitra, and Tartous saw far fewer returns. Ar-Raqqa is also an outlier: cumulative totals declined between December and July, reflecting net out-migration/secondary displacement and possible revisions to enumerations rather than steady inflows. These patterns are consistent with Raqqa's recent history of control, which has shaped both demographic change and return intentions. The city fell to opposition forces in early March 2013; ISIS then consolidated control and declared Raqqa its de facto capital in 2014; and the predominantly Kurdish Syrian Democratic Forces recaptured the city in October 2017.

Figure 1. Syrian Refugee Returns between December 8, 2024, and July 31, 2025.
Source: UNHCR, 2025 (Syria Governorates of Return Overview)

Figure 2. All Syrian Refugee Returns between 2016 and July 31, 2025
Source: UNHCR, 2025 (Syria Governorates of Return Overview)

Temporal analysis sheds further light on these dynamics. Figure 3 shows that while Aleppo and Damascus saw steady, sustained growth in return numbers, other governorates experienced more irregular trajectories, with sudden surges followed by stagnation or decline. Ar-Raqqa's early-2025 downturn indicates how quickly return gains can reverse.

The internal displacement picture is equally significant. As of July 2025, approximately 7.4 million people remain displaced within Syria's borders. Of these, 5.1 million live outside formal IDP sites, while 1.35 million reside in 1,671 camps and collective shelters across northwest and northeast Syria. Since 27 November 2024, more than 1.58 million IDPs

Figure 3. Monthly Cumulative Returns by Governorate
Source: UNHCR, 2025 (Syria Governorates of Return Overview)

For Syrian refugees, UNHCR's own intention surveys show that decisions to return are shaped by a combination of “push” factors in host countries—such as rising hostility, economic crisis, or deportation risk—and “pull” factors in Syria, including family reunification, property claims, and perceived improvements in security. Yet, as research by Kayaoglu, Sahin-Mencutek, and Erdogan (2021) and Alrababah et al. (2023) demonstrates, these “pull” factors, especially perceived safety, often remain critical but can shift rapidly. In the Syrian context, governorate-level return data confirm that security, economic opportunity, and governance quality vary so widely across the country that the calculus of return is fundamentally localized.

have returned to their areas of origin, including 774,788 who left IDP sites after 8 December 2024 (UNHCR IDP Return Overview, 2025).

Return as a Mirror of Transition

Why do these patterns matter for understanding Syria's transition? On the political front, the Asad regime's fall has increased the return numbers and intentions but has not yet translated into mass voluntary return. Economically, Syria remains in deep crisis. Infrastructure destruction and lack of basic services in many localities mean that even those willing to risk return might face formidable barriers to reintegration. In some cases,

return is also less a choice than the end point of deteriorating conditions in host states. Lebanon’s economic implosion, Turkey’s political polarization around refugee policy, and Jordan’s recalibrated approach all illustrate how host-country dynamics can also drive return patterns, although not as much as conditions inside Syria.

As Figure 4 shows, of the 746,360 people who returned between 8 December 2024 and 31 July 2025, roughly 41% originated from Lebanon ($\approx 306,760$), 36% from Turkey ($\approx 268,689$), 16% from Jordan ($\approx 119,418$), and about 7% from Iraq and Egypt combined ($\approx 55,230$), with a small remainder from other countries. Interpreted relative to refugee populations in these host countries, indicative return rates are highest in Lebanon (on the order of $\sim 30\%$), followed by Jordan ($\sim 20\%$) and Turkey ($\sim 10\%$). Returns from Europe remain negligible by comparison; for instance, only about 1,337 Syrians out of roughly 973,000 have returned from Germany after the fall of Asad (DW, 2025). These cross-country differences also demonstrate that host-states’ polit-

ical, economic, and asylum policies shape “voluntary” return. Beyond general conditions, whether protection is temporary or permanent—and whether there are pathways to longer-term residence or citizenship—plays a decisive role in refugees’ calculus to remain abroad or to return despite continuing challenges in the country of origin.

Finally, tracking not only the how many but the how and why of return is key to understanding whether Syria’s “transition” is moving toward stability or simply entering another cycle of conflict. In the end, counting returns is more than a statistical exercise. It is a means of taking the pulse of a society in flux. The patterns of who goes back, under what conditions, and with what prospects for staying offer an unvarnished view of the realities behind the headlines. In Syria, as in other post-conflict contexts, the politics of return will remain central to the politics of transition itself. ♦

Figure 4. Return by the Host Country since December 8
Source: UNHCR, 2025 (Syria Governorates of Return Overview)

References

- Alrababah, Ala', Daniel Masterson, Marine Casalis, Dominik Hangartner, and Jeremy Weinstein. 2023. "The Dynamics of Refugee Return: Syrian Refugees and Their Migration Intentions." *British Journal of Political Science* 53 (4): 1108–1131.
- Bakewell, Oliver. 1999. "Can We Ever Rely on Refugee Statistics?" *Radical Statistics* 72 (1).
- Black, Richard, and Saskia Gent. 2006. "Sustainable Return in Post-Conflict Contexts." *International Migration* 44 (1): 15–38.
- Black, Richard, and Khalid Koser, eds. 1999. *The End of the Refugee Cycle? Refugee Repatriation and Reconstruction. Forced Migration* Vol. 4. New York: Berghahn Books.
- De Haas, Hein. 2010. *Migration Transitions: A Theoretical and Empirical Inquiry into the Developmental Drivers of International Migration*. International Migration Institute Working Paper 24. University of Oxford.
- De Haas, Hein, Stephen Castles, and Mark J. Miller. 2020. *The Age of Migration: International Population Movements in the Modern World*. 6th ed. New York: Guilford Press.
- Deutsche Welle. 2025. "Germany: 1,300 Syrians Return Home Since Fall of Assad." DW, August 13.
- Kayaoglu, Ahmet, Zeynep Şahin-Mencütek, and M. Murat Erdoğan. 2021. "Return Aspirations of Syrian Refugees in Turkey." *Journal of Immigrant & Refugee Studies* 20 (4): 561–583.
- King, Russell. 1993. "Recent Immigration to Italy: Character, Causes and Consequences." *GeoJournal* 30: 283–292.
- Koser, Khalid. 2016. *International Migration: A Very Short Introduction*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR). n.d. "Global Compact for Migration."
- Şahin-Mencütek, Zeynep. 2023. *The Role of Return Preparedness, Assistance and Networks in Returnees' Reintegration in Origin Countries (Synthesis Report)*. Bonn: Bonn International Center for Conversion (BICC).
- United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR). 2025. Operational Data Portal.
- United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR). 2025. Syria Governorates IDPs and IDP Returnees Overview.
- United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR). 2025. Syria Governorates of Return Overview.

Where Were You During the Revolution? The Construction of a New Privileged Class in Post-Asad Syria¹

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“Whoever liberates decides.”

[Man yuharrir yuqarrir.]

-Popular slogan (origin unknown)

To whom does the revolution belong? In the immediate aftermath of the fall of Bashar al-Asad, euphoric proclamations of the triumph of the Syrian people were broadcast widely by the revolution’s supporters as Syria’s new rulers aimed to unify the country and allay the concerns of those who were skeptical of their intentions. Over time, the boundaries of who could claim ownership over the victory became increasingly contested. For good reason, much of the discourse examining this phenomenon has either focused on the legitimacy of the authority wielded by actors associated with Hayat Tahrir al-Sham (HTS) or rising sectarian tensions. In relation to the slogan in the epigraph, a number of critics have noted how such sentiments can have disastrous consequences in terms of the autocratization of the regime that ultimately stabilizes and the governance that follows (Ali 2025; Al-Harithi 2025). Yet, few have dis-

cussed the implications of the battle over who deserves to shape the future of Syria on the formation of a privileged class that is tied to the new governing authorities, beyond coarse examinations of sectarian identity (Ayek 2025).

This short piece is based on preliminary research into changes in social relations in Syria during the transitional period following the end of Asad’s rule. The views expressed here are provisional and draw primarily on observations from Damascus. In writing this, I was also prompted to reflect on a future that is inherently uncertain. With those caveats in mind, I contend that the transition in Syria has produced the rise of a privileged class whose identity is rooted in their presence in Idlib prior to Asad’s fall.

No social order operates independently of its political order. The political viability of a social group can shape political competition between groups, which can ultimately affect intergroup relations (Posner 2004).² More-

¹ I would like to thank Kevin Mazur and Sefa Secen for their invaluable feedback on an earlier draft of this article, and Leen Kseibi for our stimulating discussions on related topics and for drawing my attention to one of the opinion pieces cited here.

² While Posner’s focus is on political competition, he also discusses antagonistic intergroup relations.

over, just as rulers face strong incentives to limit concessions by narrowing the pool of individuals within the ruling elite (Geddes 2004), beneficiaries of the political order beyond the ruling elite may wish to limit the scope of those included in order to enjoy a greater share of the benefits. As such, the salience of various social divisions within a state is shaped by the political, social, and economic conditions of the state. In a setting where a rebel victory has completely overturned the incumbent regime and replaced its elites with a narrow group drawn from its own territory, the new governing authority's networks are likely to be tied primarily to those within the areas they previously controlled, especially when these constituents maintain ties that permeate across the country.

Moreover, where the ruling network possesses a relatively strong leader, the regime will tend toward personalism and the leader's consolidation of power (Svolik 2012, Geddes 2004). This should encourage opaqueness in decision-making and patrimonialism at the very top of the regime, which should trickle down from the ruling elite into the lower echelons of the regime's base. Emerging from this should be a broad set of individuals belonging to a relatively dense network that are tied to the regime and each other,³ and who are afforded greater access to the state.

What appears to be taking shape in Syria is the development of a privileged class that

does not map in any simple fashion onto economic strata, sect, piety, or ethnicity. Rather, while each of the above characteristics is salient to some extent, the fundamental feature of the rising social class is their connection to Idlib during the civil war. This group includes the people who are from (and stayed in) Idlib, as well as those who moved, forcibly or otherwise, to Idlib during the civil war. Many of these individuals, who certainly took on extraordinary costs, have begun to construct a narrative surrounding the revolution that centers their sacrifices and views those who remained in Asad regime-aligned territories skeptically. As such, in their view, they are an extension of the current ruling elite that produced victory over Asad, and they are the ones entitled to reap the rewards of its success.⁵

Contestation over ties to a revolutionary moment is not unique to Syria. Nevertheless, there are factors that may allow the social dynamics currently at play to produce a stable set of beneficiaries who form a privileged class in post-Asad Syria. First, there are clear historical social markers that allow individuals to differentiate class members from others. Second, those who resided in Idlib during HTS's stewardship of the Syrian Salvation Government were socialized into the norms associated with governance under HTS, providing them with an advantage in navigating state institutions during this transitional phase. Finally, and perhaps most importantly, they developed ties within the networks of

3 See El Amine and Mazur (2022) for a network-based understanding of meso-level groups.

4 In this piece, I draw on Bourdieu (1984, 114; 1985) when using the word class in a manner that extends beyond rigidly economic understandings of the term. Moreover, I emphasize the relevance of the social capital dimension perhaps to a greater extent than Bourdieu in *Distinction*, drawing on Hanna Batatu's (1979) reminder of the social networks that underly classes. It is also for this reason that I do not characterize this class as simply the state bourgeoisie (Waterbury 1991, Haddad 2012). While the burgeoning state bourgeoisie are a central feature of this class and are woven into the networks included within this privileged class, the class itself extends beyond them.

5 Of course, this does not imply that all those who resided in Idlib during the civil war carry this view.

the current ruling elite, providing them with better access to state resources than others. This further implies that they formed ties with one another, producing a network that is dense enough to potentially be a salient social grouping.

This superior social proximity to key decision-makers and others with access to decision-makers within the state not only confers upon them benefits, but also makes these individuals access points for many within the communities they are embedded in. When outside of Idlib, they become intermediaries who can decide who obtains access to influential individuals and who does not. Such individuals, particularly those with bureaucratic managerial positions, can play a role similar to that of the key (*miftah*) in the Asad regime, providing gateways to the resources of the state (Bishara 2013; Mazur 2021, 80). This positioning within Syria at a critical juncture, where the state and regime are being reshaped, could have long-term consequences on the social order.

To be clear, President Ahmed al-Sharaa's unifying statements have generally provided a broad umbrella, yet the behavior of the ruling elite since taking control of Syria has set the stage for reshaping the social order in this way. The relative power of al-Sharaa vis-à-vis his ruling network should lead to greater regime personalism (see Svolik 2012). Combined with the narrow construction of the ruling network and the general opaqueness of state management, these dynamics create conditions for a privileged class tied to the ruling elites. Even where the governing authority has attempted to resolve issues related to the opaqueness of procedures underlying recruitment, it has often centralized control over such procedures in a manner that may prevent recruitment from communities that

may be critical of actions taken by the state (see Karam Shaar Advisory Ltd. 2025A). More troubling is that the reach of the ruling elite appears to have spread quickly into the private sphere through their secretive management of the economic transition away from the business elites of the previous regime (Azhari 2025). This risks producing a crony capitalist system tied to the upper echelons of the ruling elite, similar to what emerged under Bashar al-Asad (see Haddad 2011).

These conditions are further amplified by the absence of clear ideological constraints in an atmosphere dominated by pragmatic logic. While many have worried about the Islamist or Salafist impulses of the new ruling elite, it has avoided firm ideological commitments, Islamic or otherwise, that might lead to institutionalized concessions to constituents. This has reassured some who feared the governing authority would move to impose strict religious restrictions through state institutions. Yet, the ruling elite's pragmatism has produced an opaque landscape in which the logic of survival takes precedence, potentially deepening and entrenching the privileged class as a support base that functions much like a sect or ethnic group.

Rather than delineating the boundaries of privileged access to state resources and elites through a strictly sectarian logic, which may not be feasible given the size of the sect, the most salient feature of the emerging privileged class is rooted in the social networks that developed during the civil war. This group is certainly Sunni in character, yet it excludes the vast majority of the Sunni population in Syria. While sectarian overtones may be invoked to suggest inclusion, particularly during periods of heightened sectarian tension, the fundamental structure taking

shape is more narrowly tied to a subset of Sunnis.⁶

What is outlined above is not a stable outcome but rather a trajectory I have observed with pessimism. Pressure to share power with elites drawn from other networks may lead to the building of institutions that diversify recruitment and access to the state's resources. Moreover, bottom-up pressure during this precarious period may also lead to the development of institutions that allay the concerns noted within this piece.

The actions taken by the governing authority in Syria could ultimately reshape this landscape before a relatively homogenous privileged class solidifies into a persistent feature of the social order. First, by diversifying and broadening the ruling elite with meaningful decision-making power, leaders can draw in other networks whose competing interests require the development of institutions. Second, the professionalization of bureaucracies across Syria in both recruitment and operations can help prevent the rise of such a privileged class. This requires that hiring be conducted according to clear procedures that promote merit-based practices, along with transparency in operations so that citizens can turn to state offices when needed, rather than relying on their social networks to reach a connected individual to address their concerns. The governing authority has announced several efforts aimed at the reform of the recruitment and training of state employees, yet such efforts have been piecemeal or have not yet been completely developed (Karam Shaar Advisory, Ltd. 2025B). Moreover, the initiatives proposed cannot completely resolve problems associated with shadow processes underlying access to the

state. Finally, the government's management of the economy should be done transparently, even when handling sensitive issues related to the businesses of Assad regime cronies. ♦

References

- Ali, Adnan. 2025. Man yuharrir yahkum.. maqūla nunfihā wa-nutabbiquhā. *Syria Television*, April 23. (Accessed August 24, 2025)
- Al-Harithi, Ashraf. 2025. 'An al-sulta fī Dimashq wa-l-'alāqa ma'ahā. *Al-Jumhūriyya*, April 21. (Accessed August 24, 2025)
- Ayek, Maurice. 2025. Al-Harb al-Ahliyah al-Sūriyyah fī Tawrihā al-Thānī: 'An Nihāyat Sūriyā wa-Khiyārāt Mustaqbal 'al-Aghyār' Khārijahā. *Al-Jumhūriyya*, August 22. (Accessed August 29, 2025)
- Azhari, Timour and Feras Dalatey. 2025. "Syria is secretly reshaping its economy. The president's brother is in charge." *Reuters*, July 24. (Accessed August 24, 2025)
- Batatu, Hanna. 1979. "Class analysis and Iraqi society." *Arab Studies Quarterly* 1(3): 229-244.
- Bishara, Azmi. 2013. *Sūriyah: Darb al-Ālām nahw al-Hurriyyah – Muhāwala fī al-Tārīkh al-Rāhin*. Doha: Arab Center for Research and Policy Studies.
- Bourdieu, Pierre. 1984. *Distinction: A Social Critique of the Judgement of Taste*. Translated by Richard Nice. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Bourdieu, Pierre. 1985. "The social space and the genesis of groups." *Social Science Information*, 24(2): 195-220.

⁶ This does not imply that sectarian divisions have not led to chauvinism or a callous disregard for the fears of non-Sunni communities among some.

El Amine, Loubna and Kevin Mazur. 2022. "Thinking about groups in political science: A case for bringing the meso level back in." *Political Science Quarterly*, 137(2): 331–355.

Karam Shaar Advisory LTD. 2025A. "Opaque Appointments: Ministerial Advisors and Assistants in Syria." *Syria in Figures*, 11. Accessed September 20, 2025.

_____. 2025B. "The Syrian Public Sector: Restructuring the State After Assad." *Syria in Figures*, 11. Accessed September 20, 2025.

Geddes, Barbara. 2004. "Minimum-winning coalitions and personalization in authoritarian regimes." *Annual Meeting of the American Political Science Association*, Chicago.

Haddad, Bassam. 2011. *Business Networks in Syria: The Political Economy of Authoritarian Resilience*. Stanford University Press.

_____. 2012. "Syria's state bourgeoisie: An organic backbone for the regime." *Middle East Critique*, 21(3): 231-257.

Mazur, Kevin. 2021. *Revolution in Syria: Identity, Networks, and Repression*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Posner, Daniel N. 2004). "The political salience of cultural difference: Why Chewas and Tumbukas are allies in Zambia and adversaries in Malawi." *American Political Science Review*, 98(4): 529–545.

Svolik, Milan. 2012. *The Politics of Authoritarian Rule*. Cambridge University Press.

Roundtable Discussion:

Social Science Funding and Knowledge Production During Turbulent Times: Reflections From MENA Scholars

Diana B. Greenwald in conversation with Lisa Anderson, Sofia Fenner, Ellen Lust, Jamil Mouawad, Salma Mousa

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Introduction, by Diana B. Greenwald

On October 2, 2025, we convened a virtual roundtable to discuss the state of funding for social science research in and on the MENA region. To reflect on this topic, we invited five scholars who are at various stages in their careers, whose work represents diverse epistemological and methodological approaches, and who have drawn on a range of types of resources to fund their work. An edited transcript of our conversation follows below.

One question that hovered over much of our conversation was: How exceptional is the present moment? Some of the challenges that scholars in our field face seem like stable, if not permanent, features of the landscape. We touch on these in our discussion: For example, the inevitable ways that politics, including donor priorities, shape research, and the sometimes frustrating role of other “gate-keepers”, such as institutional review

boards. Yet, recent months have also seen a rapid accumulation of acute shocks. In the US, in particular, MENA scholars have not been immune from the Trump administration’s jarring, multidimensional assault on academic research and higher education. President Trump has overseen the termination of National Science Foundation (NSF)-funded projects and reductions that, as of mid-2025, had brought scientific research awards in the US to [their lowest rate in decades](#). The National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) was similarly targeted for drastic cuts and [subsequent funding](#) was allocated to topics aligned with President Trump’s ideological agenda. The executive branch has [seized control of the United States Institute of Peace](#), which funded a well-known dissertation fellowship, among other things, and gutted its existing staff. Federal budget appropriations remain very much in flux as, at the time of

writing, the US is in its third week of a government shutdown. Scholars from select countries in the region – including Iran, Libya, Sudan, and Yemen – have been banned from entering the US [under a June 2025 executive order](#). Further, efforts by the US government, state governments, and academic institutions to surveil, control, and suppress speech and protest on Palestine has contributed to a climate of insecurity and fear, with particularly existential consequences for non-citizen and immigrant members of our community. Most of these actions and policies have been, and continue to be, challenged in court. In the meantime, we are all feeling these silencing pressure from above in different ways, and to varying degrees.

Our contributors reflect on what a potential longer term retreat in US funding might mean for individual scholars and knowledge production, more broadly. We agreed that those of us who have had the benefit of working in relatively open and unrestricted settings now have much to learn from those who have not. Despite an overall sense that the environment for field-based political science research in MENA has become more constrained in recent years, contributors emphasized how scholars might nonetheless navigate this environment and pursue strategic opportunities by, for example, exploring lesser-known sources of social science funding in the region; adopting a form of bricolage to draw on disparate resources, institutions, and relationships to support their research; turning to epistemological and methodological approaches that might be both lower cost and more resilient to political shocks (here, our contributors reflect on both interpretivist methods and the analysis of unstructured “big data”); and creatively redefining what constitutes “the field” when certain populations and geographies are inaccessible.

However, not all of these strategies – which call for nimbleness, flexibility, and creative retooling – are available to all scholars at all times. The way forward, as it emerges from our conversation, places significant burdens on researchers, and early-career and untenured scholars will be disproportionately affected.

Many scholars based in the region have become accustomed to navigating authoritarian institutions and practices, active conflict zones, and conditions of seemingly self-perpetuating volatility and crisis. As higher educational and research institutions in the MENA region have been either unable or unwilling to invest significantly in social science research, roundtable participants reflect on how MENA-based social scientists have increasingly turned to sources of non-academic research funding and the sometimes worrying implications of this trend. In addition to some of these more structural or slower moving trends in the region itself, certain equilibria seem to have been shattered in recent years. The war in Sudan, which began in April 2023, has been defined by atrocious war crimes, upending the lives of tens of millions of people, resulting in mass displacement, famine, and what has been described as [one of the largest humanitarian crises ever recorded](#). Following the October 7, 2023 Hamas-led attacks, Israel’s genocidal war in Gaza has devastated a people, laying waste to their cities and neighborhoods, their historic sites, their homes, their storefronts, their infrastructure, their universities, their places of worship, their farms, and their land. The expansion of Israel’s war fronts into Lebanon, Iran, Syria, Yemen, and even, for a moment, Qatar layered new destruction and instability on top of existing challenges and crises. It may be too early to catalog the myriad ways in which these events will shape scholarship

and knowledge production. Even as pages of documentation, archival material, theoretical advances, and new empirical findings are constructed in the months and years ahead, we may never know how much has been permanently lost.

Edited Transcript

Diana B. Greenwald (DG): I thought that we could begin this conversation on research funding by drawing on [a recent piece](#) that, Ellen, you've recently written on this topic, with Samuel Tafesse Wakuma, in the *Daedalus special issue* that was co-edited by Lisa with Rabab El-Mahdi and Seteney Shami. You've written this piece on the economics of social science research and knowledge production in the Middle East and North Africa. There are a number of findings from this dataset that you built and analyzed in the piece. One of the findings that stood out to me was that research funding coming from sources within the region is dwarfed by funding resources from outside the region. Also, the substance and nature of research seems to vary depending on the funding sources. So, I thought maybe the findings from this article could be a good launching point for our conversation. Ellen, do you want to summarize some of the key points there, and some of the arguments you develop about these differences in the origins of research funding and the implications that has for social science knowledge production?

Ellen Lust (EL): Sure, and I should preface this by saying that the kind of research funding that we're able to look at in this piece is primarily that given by large organizations like the National Science Foundation or Swedish Research Council. It tends to be the kind of grants that go to university researchers, people like us, and then gets distributed.

We're not looking at, for example, funding for consultancies, including everything from the World Bank and [United Nations Development Program] UNDP to smaller consultancies or privately funded research, which often have a research component to them. You may end up with a slightly different picture if you include other types of funding.

In terms of thinking about the research funding that is going to universities: First of all, yes, it is definitely the case that research funding in Europe and in the United States, at least until very recently, has far outstripped what there is in the region. It's also worth remembering that so has just the preponderance of researchers. So, you're looking, in the region, at a lot of universities that don't even have social science departments. Social sciences, unsurprisingly, are not where authoritarian regimes invest a lot of energy or national resources. According to the [2021 UNESCO Science Report](#), research investment by Arab states is quite low relative to other regions, and it's even lower when it comes to research investment into social sciences. So, when you take all of those things into account, you find that the vast majority of research funding for the type of research that most academics do is coming out of the US and Europe.

It's not very surprising that these countries are interested in funding the research that they think matters to them. We would expect national interests to drive funding. But the focus on national interests means that political science dominates European- and US-based research, and that there is greater emphasis on issues like migration in European-funded research and security issues in research funded from the US. The problem isn't necessarily that Europeans are interested in migration because they think that has implications for

them, or that the US is interested in what they see as security issues because they want to inform their foreign policy. We should anticipate that.

The problem arises because there is an imbalance in the sources of resources for research and this creates an imbalance in terms of what gets understood. The topics that people in the region care about are not necessarily the topics that then get studied. If you look at what sort of research appears to be of interest to researchers in the Middle East, North Africa, or [Southwest Asia and North Africa] SWANA region, you're seeing that it's environmental and social issues, and other things that we don't really see prioritized.

So to me, it's interesting to think about how a potential longer term decline of US-based funding will affect our understanding of the region. Does it mean that you'll see an uptick of funding from elsewhere? Does it mean that basically we just see much less knowledge being generated in English about the SWANA region to begin with? I'm not entirely sure. I think that's something we can all discuss.

The other thing I want to highlight, which is less about research funding but is really important to think through, is how we understand the knowledge landscape itself. These big gaps in knowledge are not only about donor priorities and research funding; they are also about what reviewers think is important and what gets rewarded if you are going up for tenure, for example. So, it's not simply the US government's interest or European governments' interests, but also scholars' priorities, that shape our knowledge.

Finally, I want to note that research being done in various places, such as in consultancies or international organizations, is often

not made public. Most of us don't see that research or its results. That is an important type of gap when trying to better understand research production in and on the region.

DG: Yeah, thanks for that. It is also worth noting that, in this article, you are looking at relatively recent grant awards from 2016 to 2021. But, in terms of some of those general observations, which among these are more recent and which are maybe longer-term trends? For example, this regional imbalance in terms of the sources of social science funding, and also, as Ellen's pointing out, a lot of the results of research on MENA do not ultimately make it into the public sphere, or into scholarly publications, and it's sort of hidden from view.

Lisa Anderson (LA): Actually, as I was thinking about this, I don't think that funding for research, probably anywhere and ever, but particularly in my professional life around the Middle East, has ever not been driven by political imperatives. The conceit that we spend a lot of time fostering – that there was something that was completely independent research, and that had no political context or motive – you know... that clearly was wrong, always, and forever. So, then the question is: are there differences now in sources of funding that will reflect different kinds of political interests? If the United States in general is going to be funding less, will that be reflected just in volume – will there just be less research? – or will the political coloration of the research that's done change?

So I think there are going to be a variety of subsidiary questions, but one question I don't think we should spend much time on is whether there are political agendas in research. There clearly are, and there always have been, and American foundations, when

they were funding, they could be sort of adjacent to government funding, but they were not unaffected by government funding, even in the best, most politically pluralistic moments. For instance, I was early to understand that, since I could not get a Fulbright to go to Libya because the American government said no, at the end of the day, I was in one of those sort of pluralistic moments when the Social Science Research Council was funding dissertation research, and they were willing to fund my travel. But, you know, that SSRC funding came from big foundations, that came from the Ford Foundation. Ford, in the intervening decades, has been, among many other foundations, under enormous pressure not to fund what could be construed as support of terrorist organizations, or even “terrorist sympathizers,” through laws on money-laundering, sanctions, and so forth. So, the space to be adjacent to the American government, supplementing and widening the research landscape, has shrunk. Partly as a result major foundations have turned to less contentious arenas and particularly to back-filling where the US government is no longer supporting work domestically.

But in any event, I think some of these conditions have been familiar to us for a long time, and some of them have become more constraining.

DG: Yeah, I think we could probably identify some turning points or key moments.

LA: 9/11 made a big difference.

DG: Yeah. Salma, Go ahead.

SALMA MOUSA (SM): Yeah, thank you. It's really nice to be in all of your company, and to hear all of this.

I just wanted to raise two points. The first is when we say a lot of this funding of MENA research comes from abroad, I think one somewhat unfortunate thing is that there are actually pockets in the Middle East that have a lot of money that they could be spending on research funding. The Doha Institute, [and its affiliated Arab Center for Research and Policy Studies,] for example, and other big institutes in the Gulf that are kind of half think tank but also have graduate programs. They are research- and teaching-oriented, and presumably have money to be funding international, competitive grants. They have launched large-scale data collection initiatives too, like the [Arab Opinion Index](#), so there is an appreciation of quantitative research. But given the way that field experiments and large-scale quantitative work has evolved in the U.S., there may be an underappreciation of how much it costs to do research that requires collecting original data at scale, and I think that's unfortunate.

My second point is regarding these big funders from the US, the UK, and Europe like [the Abdul Latif Jameel Poverty Action Lab] J-PAL, Innovations for Poverty Action, or Center for Economic Policy Research. They have money, and they fund projects on the Middle East, but they get to decide, of course, their priority countries. And it's always kind of unclear to me how those countries are chosen. This year, it's Syria and Turkey and Yemen. So, if you have a project on, for instance, Egypt, that's not a priority country. There could be some more transparency into the process of determining priority countries, and where there is, it's often tied to the policy priorities of the funding government or organization. I actually once tried to submit a proposal for a project funded by the British foreign ministry, that would have included a component in the West Bank, and

the donor rejected it, saying we don't fund work in "developed countries", basically implying that the West Bank was Israel. So, that's at the extreme end, but I think this classification of priority countries, and what's considered a developing country versus developed, takes away a lot of power from researchers, I think, to pursue what they think is good work. And it's really unfortunate that even those who do have the money in the Middle East are not actually funding research grants, which would, I think, help a lot.

DG: Yeah, thanks for that perspective, Salma, since some of those institutions are, not necessarily ones that we would have centrally considered otherwise, J-PAL and others, like the World Bank, for example. And maybe that's something to acknowledge as well in this conversation, is that different institutions have different sorts of knowledge bases about the region, and ways that they do or do not understand politics in the region, and then that shapes their priorities. Economists, for example, will come from a different knowledge base and different perspective.

SM: Yeah, that's a whole other conversation. But, I think sometimes it can be good to have people who are doing work on the region who actually don't have as much country-specific knowledge. Sometimes it helps when you take a step back and just treat it as any other country, in a way. Not always, but sometimes. For example, there is [this paper by Bursztyn et al.](#) about correcting misperceptions about social norms about female labor market participation in Saudi Arabia. Basically, most men think that other men are not cool with their wives and sisters working, but, in fact, most of them are pretty cool with it. So, once you tell them that, their wives and sisters are more likely to apply for jobs. And I think it's a really cool paper. It's published in

the [American Economic Review] AER, a top economics journal.

And I have seen certain takedowns of [randomized controlled trials] RCTs in the Middle East, and they don't really critique the substance of the studies. Some studies, like the one I mentioned, actually did something that was probably helpful in that society. So, I think it can be unfortunate when we restrict ourselves in that way. There is some good work about the Middle East, not necessarily by Middle Eastern researchers, that comes from that economics perspective. I think there are some problems with it, for sure, but well-articulated critiques of these problems should deal with the substance of the research.

EL: What I think both Lisa and Salma's comments suggest is the importance of pluralism – whether we're talking about pluralism in funding, or we're talking about pluralism in methodologies, countries, or the perspectives from which people approach these various problems. And I think that the real concern is when you lose that. We shouldn't expect any funder, whether it's the World Bank or governments or foundations, to be funding outside of their interests. So, the important question is how many different interests can be at the table, providing funding?

Yes, the institutions in the Gulf can do more, but, more generally, I think it's good to have a variety and a wide range of approaches and interests coming into the landscape.

SM: Also, I just remembered that J-PAL actually opened an office at [the American University in Cairo] AUC. So there's a J-PAL MENA office now, which I think is huge, and they are funding work all across the Middle East. They're based in Cairo, and you can

draw on their resources. So, for example, the [Institutional Review Board] IRB research managers that they assign you will be based in Egypt to help run the project.

They even supported qualitative researchers for our project, so they sent people all over Egypt to do interviews with our research participants. So, they weren't so dogmatic about the approach. They were really open to adding these qualitative components, and that's really nice, because that's completely administered by people at AUC. Funding opportunities here include the Air and Water lab at the Hub of Advanced Policy Innovation for the Environment ([HAPIE](#)), and the [Egypt Impact Lab](#). Yes, it is tied a little bit still to the economic development perspective. And the goals have to somewhat be aligned with goals that the Egyptian government is okay with – for example, outcomes like health and education and family planning. You can't be too risky. But if your research happens to fall within that bucket, that's a bright spot I want to highlight for others, because I don't think enough people know about it. I think they actually have quite a lot of funding.

DG: Thanks for that. We have a diverse readership, so, you know, I think we're hoping that junior scholars reading the newsletter can benefit from some of these insights, tips, and perspectives.

Sofia Fenner (SF): It's really interesting to hear all of these sort of institutional perspectives, because I think I approached this question very differently, which was a question about what researchers do given certain challenges, one of which is funding, but I think just to name the thing, the biggest challenge is authoritarianism. That has always been the biggest challenge, and that remains the biggest challenge, I think, for both scholars in

the region and scholars outside of the region, and that hasn't changed.

So, from a qualitative perspective, and really from an interpretive perspective, I think that one of the great virtues of certain kinds of qualitative research is that they are cheap—relatively cheap—and also relatively adaptable to circumstances. Often, especially at an early career stage, the only thing a researcher really needs is a plane ticket and somewhere to live. That's the kind of funding that you can cobble together from all kinds of sources; you don't need massive grants that can really only come from institutions or governments, whether in the region or outside of it. If you speak the dialect that you need to speak to be doing the research that you're doing, you don't need to hire a translator. You don't need to hire an interpreter. Again, to Lisa's point, independent research has always been sort of a fiction, but I think there are ways to make research cheaper, and thereby maybe construct a certain kind of autonomy. It won't work for everybody, and it won't work for all methods, but I think this is one of those moments when certain kinds of qualitative methods really have an advantage: that they simply don't cost as much money as a randomized controlled trial, or a survey, or some of this really fascinating, scaled work that, unfortunately, is very expensive.

Historical research can also be inexpensive if you can get to an archive, or if the archive is available somewhere that you can access. Even if you can't get local government approval, or you can't get a lot of funding from US or European institutions, you might still be able to get access to archival materials. Many qualitative researchers will say, “Yeah, I'm a comparative historical researcher,” but are we actually trained as historians? Do we actually have the skills required to work with

primary sources? Because once we have those skills, we're empowered to do kinds of research that can slip under the radar in certain ways while still speaking to central social science questions.

Thinking about ways that we can continue to generate knowledge and continue to have conversations in a world where we have fewer funding sources involves taking a look at not just qualitative methods, but also interpretive epistemologies and ontologies.

So, for example, sometimes when you're dealing with a difficult funding situation, or a difficult political situation, or both, there happens to be a place you can go and learn *something*, but you don't necessarily know what it is yet. That situation isn't going to meet positivist standards of case selection, or representativeness, or any of those other things. And the discipline's not super well positioned, and especially young scholars are often not well positioned, to defend or accept the knowledge production capacity of a research design that's honest about its origins: "This was a place I could go at a time where I had money to be there, and I didn't really know what I was going to find, and this is what I found." We should be open to funding projects that might be less structured in their research design and that are open to responding to local political conditions. Maybe you did have a relationship with a local institution, and maybe that disintegrates for any of a variety of reasons. What does ethics look like now?

I'm thinking about how we can build, for lack of a better word, scrappiness into research designs, and how we can respect and honor research designs that have that scrappiness. And really acknowledge the ways in which such projects contribute to knowledge accu-

mulation.

For me, not so much because of funding, but

because of politics, that's the direction that I am moving towards. Safe, ethical, ethnographic research in the region seems like it is becoming more and more difficult. One of the ways we can cope with that is to move to the past in a really meaningful sense: to work with primary sources, ask questions about "the archive," and maybe become a little more comfortable with uncertainty. If political science becomes de-emphasized because of a lack of funding from the United States, maybe history, anthropology—other kinds of approaches many of us are adjacent to already—move in to take up some of that space. Maybe this is a time to lean in that direction, and to collaborate across borders, but also across disciplines. Historians never have enough money to make it to the past. No one can go to the past! I think there's a lot of potential there.

We are sort of a magpie discipline. We like to steal other disciplines' methods and adapt them to our own purposes. It might be a good time to lean into methods that are more "instability-proof" – I don't know if that's the right term for it – but methods that give us a little bit more maneuvering room, no matter where we are, or who we are.

EL: Can I chime in here? I recognize this might be taking us a little bit afar, but what I like about that, Sofia, is that it's not just about historical research being less expensive. The challenge in the way that we've done things in political science is that we are often responding to the immediate crisis and need. 9/11 happened, and we all wanted to study radical Islamists. Then something else happens, and

we all want to study whatever the next wave is. But essentially, we are not well situated to study radical Islamists in the moment when they're at their height and before anything else changes. And by the time we're starting to see some interesting changes among Islamist movements and radical Islam, then we've all moved on to something else. So, the advantage of studying the past is that we can actually do what, in a sense, we should be doing anyway – really be studying from a perspective where we can more easily separate trajectories and have a better understanding of the fuller picture of the things that we study. So I think there's an argument to be made that goes beyond the funding, logistics, and what's feasible and to really think about how incorporating a historical perspective may help us actually change the way in which we gain knowledge and understand it. It doesn't work for everything, but for some things, it might be superior.

SF: Yes! I am at a small liberal arts college (SLAC) that is primarily and overwhelmingly focused on undergraduate teaching, and that obviously creates some research and funding challenges of its own. But I think it also opens up certain possibilities. For example, we have very different tenure expectations, so there's nothing wrong with publishing as a political scientist primarily in non-political science journals, i.e. in area studies journals, historical journals, literary studies journals, or anywhere else. At certain universities, that would be a real career problem. But in other places it's not; indeed, it's sometimes seen as a virtue!

It's odd because I'm used to looking with a certain amount of envy at the research support that's available at research-oriented institutions and universities. But I've come to appreciate the flexibility afforded by a differ-

ent way of approaching career incentives. In navigating this funding environment, being at a SLAC feels very much like a privilege right now. I think it would be very difficult if I were somewhere where the tenure standards expected me to do very large-scale work very quickly and publish it only in political science journals. I would be feeling a lot more uncertain than I am now.

In fact, thinking about where knowledge lives and how it's reproduced, and where it's stored and conserved during periods of difficulty, might also invite us to think a little bit differently about the role of different kinds of institutions, both here and elsewhere, in knowledge production.

DG: Thank you, Sofia and Ellen as well for that, and I want to welcome Jamil, who was having some electricity issues, but has now rejoined us. Welcome.

JAMIL MOUAWAD (JM): Again, thanks for having me. One issue that I think is important to highlight is the role of the IRB and the concepts of risk. Of course, I'm speaking to you from the region, and here we are caught between the imperatives of the IRB and the reality we live in. Risk is part of our daily life. So, assessing risk from the vantage point of the IRB might differ entirely from how we, in our context and experience, feel and perceive it. And this lens is a tool now, I'm afraid, that contributes to the construction of the region as a “security threat”. So, of course, the region is a threat for some researchers. We've seen some very unfortunate incidents with PhD students in Egypt, for example, and elsewhere in the region, but it doesn't mean that we only have to look at the region from a risk perspective, or from a threat perspective. The IRBs as institutions were essentially designed in the West and

then traveled to, and land in, our institutions here. They tend to approach the region through a security lens, thereby shaping it as a site of potential threat. So the IRB has an impact, which is constructing the region as a security threat, and contributing to over-scrutinizing the region at the same time.

The threat that an IRB committee member sometimes sees is in fact my daily life – my daily reality. So imagine Arab students working on their PhDs in Europe or in the US and they are not granted permission to go and do their fieldwork while their parents live here, or even to come and stay for holidays. So there is a discrepancy between the requirements and the way the IRB looks at the region and the reality of the region. And this should be addressed. This is [the work we've been doing](#) at the Arab Council for Social Sciences (ACSS), in a way – trying to move away from treating ethics as just a checklist and look, rather, at indigenous understanding of ethics.

Let's look at ethics as situational, as an encounter, and not only as a tool to give a green or red light to what to do, what topics we should work on, and whatnot.

And the second point that I would like to raise is that ethics can sometimes be used as an alibi to censor research, whether by governments, universities, or even professors. They take advantage of this, and they do censor research by saying it has to go through the IRB. So, the IRB here is no longer a tool to safeguard the researcher and protect participants. It's also a tool to censor research, to control what kind of questions can be asked, and what kind of knowledge is acceptable or not. This is very unfortunate.

The third point I'd like to make is that I've

had many students, for example, students working on their MA thesis, and they avoid the IRB, because it takes a lot of time and the application is way too long. So they end up relying on secondary resources for their MAs, and we're missing a very good opportunity to produce original research, from students who are based in the region and in the field, and can indeed produce very original analysis that is otherwise not always accessible for those who are studying the region but are not based in the region. Instead, students end up being disconnected from the field – even though they live in the region – because simply the IRB becomes too cumbersome and time-consuming. They want to graduate to go on the job market. So, there is an imperative to rethink IRB. Of course, it doesn't mean that we should not be part of the promotion of the culture of ethics in social sciences and humanities, especially in the Arab world. We need it, but it shouldn't act as a tool to censor research and prevent the production of original knowledge.

And funding is part of this, because I know at the ACSS that they require applicants to fill out a questionnaire on ethics. This is a good thing to do, but again, it shouldn't be a reason why we grant or we don't grant access to the field. Because already those researchers are in the field. Risk is there. Risk, as I said, is part of their everyday life.

SF: On this note, I think it's less common for qualitative researchers who go through an IRB process to have a local IRB partner, partly because the simple fact of that is actually exposing everyone involved to more risk than they might otherwise be exposed to.

That is part of why there needs to be a robust discussion, especially among qualitative researchers, about the ethics of what we're

doing and how we're doing it. There needs to be real dialogue about what informed consent means and about information practices, because honestly, the IRB system in the United States doesn't hold certain kinds of qualitative research to as high a standard as I think it should. Partly because it doesn't really recognize them as valid forms of research, right? What harm could possibly come of just asking people questions and listening to the answers? The IRB system isn't designed for that kind of research or for the dangers it poses.

LA: I'd just like to follow up a little bit on this, and Sofia, I think you're a little bit more generous about this than I'm about to be. It's really about risk management for the institutions. It's not, in fact, about ethics or even risk management for individual researchers. Honestly, I don't think most of the institutions that have IRBs care very much about the safety and security of the researchers. They just know that it's bad for reputation management if something happens to somebody. So it's almost hostile to research. You know, it's sort of, "We have to let you do it, because we're supposed to let you do it, but life would be much easier if none of you did research." And so let's narrow it as much as possible, make it as "safe" as possible, and make it as risk-free as possible.

There's an almost self-defeating quality in some of the ways IRBs, and General Counsel's offices, operate these days, because you can see that they would just prefer nobody did any research, because somehow it's going to be a problem for them. So, I think this is a fundamental problem, and I don't see how, as IRBs are currently constructed, that they would be able to absorb the scrappiness in the kinds of research that Sofia was encouraging earlier. I just don't see how they're going

to be able to say, "Yeah, go ahead and see what happens." I mean, that's not how they're designed at this point.

So I think we need to think about the various gatekeepers for research. One of them is IRBs and the institutions that are supposed to be fostering research. Another is, of course, funders. Funders are going to foster the kind of research that they think is valuable, but it may not be the kind of research that any of us want to do. There are a bunch of gatekeepers of research and we can't be totally free-wheeling and do what we want, for a variety of reasons. In fact, I think that the environment for research has actually become more constrained over time. So, yeah, I did a comparative study of Tunisia and Libya, not because I had an elegant comparative research design but because I needed a fall-back since I wasn't sure I'd get a visa to Libya. Full stop.

That's not a good argument for the comparison, but it was the underlying rationale for the comparison, and then I developed something that I thought made a great deal of sense. And, in fact, I found things I didn't expect. I would never have been able to tell the IRB that. I do think the context, the institutional framework for research, has become quite deliberately discouraging.

So, Diana, if I may, I think one of the things that has come up as a productive way of looking at this is a kind of bricolage. You know: maybe you can do something with J-PAL, maybe you can do something in the archives, and so forth. It rests with the researcher to be creative about that, to learn that this kind of work would be possible in Egypt if I work with J-PAL, or this might be possible in Libya if I can get into the archives, et cetera.

I think there are opportunities like that to be

creative. However, there are two difficulties that I would flag. First, it really does burden the researcher to be not only intellectually creative, but also institutionally knowledgeable to figure out where the space is. For example, you can work on climate, and maybe you'll get some funding because the climate people have some money...All of us need to be thinking in that way more than we typically do. We're just sort of waiting for the funding to come to do whatever we want, and that's obviously not happening. So it does burden the researcher a little, you know. I'm thinking of early-career people doing their PhDs trying to figure out where these opportunities are.

The second question is an ethical issue. If this is a productive approach to, for example, tag along with the World Bank, or tag along with J-PAL, or tag along with some other organization, to what extent are you being completely candid with the people you're tagging along with about the research you're doing? Is it shaping, or even distorting or warping, what you want to do, and to what extent are you being candid, even with yourself, about that? Because these opportunities are genuinely there, but they may also be [what Sarah Parkinson calls](#) "dual hatting." So, for example, you are going out as an embed in the military in Iraq and doing your PhD at the same time. Is that okay? Or, more ambiguously, what if you're doing something as a consultant? What are the guidelines there, not only for IRBs, but for ourselves, so that we can say, "Everybody knows what I am doing, everybody knows why I am doing it, everybody knows this is what I might contribute to the larger project, and this is where the limits of my contributions are going to be. Everybody knows that I am going to publish this, whatever the terms of the funders are." I think there's going to be more and more of that

kind of arrangement, and we haven't entirely thought through how to provide guidance on what that relationship should look like as a junior early career person interacts with that research institution and with their home department. So I think there are opportunities, but they are also going to be providing us with new questions.

EL: I agree with much of what you say, Lisa. How do we understand what the real opportunities are, what does it mean to be consulting, and frankly, what are some of the challenges with that?

You know, sometimes you feel perfectly fine with the project you are on, and you feel perfectly fine with the expectations, and you have been very upfront about the fact that you will use this data to publish. And the organization you are working with says, "That's great, and that can be done as soon as we have published our own report," and then, for internal political reasons, they decide never to do that. So, then you are basically up a creek. You have essentially subsidized a relatively powerful organization and suddenly you are out of luck because you can't use the data.

Scholars trying to navigate these relationships benefit from the kinds of conversations and communities that [the Research Ethics in the Middle East and North Africa \(REME-NA\) project](#) has built and is building, that [the Project on Middle East Political Science \(POMEPS\)](#) has built and is building. That's great for everybody who has access to those conversations. However, lots of PhD students working on the region are actually not in places where their advisors know the region or are well-connected to these communities. So, I think we need to consider how we, as a community, can make sure that we are not

just reaching those PhD students whose advisors can connect them into POMEPS or REMENA, for example, but we are including people who are not at those institutions. How can we commit ...to make sure that the impact doesn't remain within a smaller set of people who are interested and care about the region, but rather expand these conversations to a fuller set of young scholars?

SF: But also, Lisa and Ellen, hearing you talk about this just makes me think: This discussion is itself a fascinating social science topic! How do people generate knowledge in circumstances where funding is constrained, where freedom of choice and expression are constrained, where there are power imbalances involved that are really important? The people who have the most experience with trying to do research under those circumstances are scholars in the region.

So, I think this is a really interesting opportunity to say: Well, how have the scholars I know in Egypt historically navigated conflicts of interest, or those “double-hatting” situations? How have they honored the principle of transparency when they can't necessarily be transparent vis-a-vis their governments? And how do they think about the ethics of that? Those of us who have had the privilege of working in relatively open environments have a lot to learn from those who haven't.

LA: I just have one quick crack about that, if I may, because I completely agree with you. I have been corresponding with a Libyan colleague about some work that we're doing together. I apologized to him for being distracted, because, as we all know, Columbia University has been in a lot of upheaval. He wrote back and said, “Yeah, it's been like that here for 45 years.”

DG: These reflections and guidance are all really helpful. If we look at some of REMENA's recommendations, we see that they are geared toward trying to promote more collaboration with institutions and scholars based in the region, and to have those forms of collaboration be supported throughout the whole ecosystem, funding included. So, I think getting a sense of the climate for social science research in the region would be really helpful for this discussion. Jamil, I certainly don't intend to make you a representative of the MENA region, but...

JM: Yes, I am “the local.” [laughs]

DG: [laughs] Right. But I do have questions about this. Maybe you can give us a sense of what it looks like for PhD students or junior faculty members in MENA trying to get social science research support. Earlier in the conversation, we touched on the role of some of the big academic institutes in Doha and elsewhere in the Gulf, for example. But, across the region as a whole, what role do different types of universities and research institutions play in, in funding or supporting – or not funding and not supporting – social science research?

JM: I mean, Doha and the Gulf is one set of cases, and then other universities in, for example, Egypt, Palestine, and Lebanon, maybe this is another set of cases where funds and resources are less available; partially because of the political economy of these countries and the ongoing political crises, including refugee displacement, wars, and even instances of genocide. These problems, to a certain extent, define the knowledge we produce. The knowledge production is now dictated to a certain extent by funding, and those who are being funded the most are NGOs or think tanks. This is based on the assumption that

their reports can be produced quickly and are necessary to address such pressing issues and challenges. This has implications on the kind of knowledge we produce, and the reality we are constructing.

So, it's a fairly easy way to go and get money, and then you produce research and knowledge that does not always have the same methodological rigor as studies that follow academic criteria. Maybe this research is not ethical in itself. For instance, imagine the number of reports that were published by NGOs on refugees with no ethical consideration whatsoever. Most of these reports are not peer-reviewed – I'm talking here about international, but also local and national, NGOs. Funding at the university looks far more complicated, and it's more challenging to obtain than funding at an NGO or an international organization. So here, I refer to the point that Lisa brought up, which is working as a consultant. At the end of the day, given the political economy of the region and the political economy of our profession, you might end up accepting to work as a consultant for a UN agency, and this introduces completely different parameters for doing research, because you know that you have to write something that they would eventually accept, which secures for you yet another consultancy. In some instances, we lose the purpose of knowledge, which is to speak truth to power. It is a completely different framework than what we use when publishing in a peer-reviewed journal, or presenting a paper in an academic conference. This has an impact on knowledge production. It is an epistemological question. In the region right now, it is often far easier for me to go and write a report for a NGO than to, for example, get funds to do fieldwork for an article that I would submit to a peer-reviewed journal; an article that takes two years to produce

and another one to publish.

A second point is that we should acknowledge that “the field” is not accessible in the region, or at least it is less and less accessible, due to wars in places like Syria, Lebanon, Palestine, and Yemen. But there is also a way to look at the field not as a physical space, but also the field as bricolage, and I'm using the word here offered earlier by Lisa. Bricolage means we need to rethink and be creative on how we construct the field by assembling different methods and techniques, even if we're not in this region. We need to gather different sets of methods and construct our own field. So someone living in the US working on Palestine, he or she cannot access the field, that's for sure, but they can recruit local researchers, train local researchers, they can do digital anthropology, et cetera. So we really need to be creative when it comes to trying to construct our own fields. And this is often not fully appreciated or captured by donors. They are used to mainstream political science that is very much based on quantitative research, but we do need to be creative and carve out more space for interpretivist approaches to the field.

So, this is something scholars in the region have been thinking about a lot. The field as bricolage, as Lisa puts it, and as an alternative to field inaccessibility. Here, we can talk more about partnerships between those who are in the US or Europe and us local scholars or researchers working in the region. So we have to be creative in this sense.

DG: We are running up against the clock, but another thing we haven't touched on are other research methods that are generally less expensive. This includes work that is remotely based, maybe computationally intensive, perhaps even using newly digitized archival

sources, or things that you can do a little bit more easily. And so, in a sense, that is a very different approach, but it ties into this idea that Jamil is referencing of reinterpreting the field and what becomes “the field” for us in these circumstances. Any thoughts on that, Salma, or others?

SM: Yes. Well, at UCLA we have even less research funding than we had before, so when I'm advising graduate students, I do encourage them to consider learning how to use these AI tools for scraping social media, websites, administrative data, and the like. There is a lot of free data. Go to the [World Values Survey](#), go to the [Arab Barometer](#), go to the general social surveys, the [Gallup World Poll](#), et cetera. There is so much data out there. Learn to scrape newspaper articles, do a sentiment analysis, code up how people are talking about certain topics. Even if you are doing qualitative interviews: For example, if you conduct interviews with 50 people, and there is a roughly 20-page transcript for each person, you can actually code up what people are talking about, you can systematically label them using ChatGPT and tools like that, and all of that is basically free. So I'm really moving students to try to find data that is already out there in the world, and just learn the skills to actually use that stuff. We don't have much funding anymore anyway, and this data is really rich and probably underexplored. It is highly unstructured, and this unstructured data is where we get so much leverage from AI, as opposed to survey data, for example. I know I mentioned survey data as well, but this unstructured data – like images and text – those are the kinds of things where researchers, especially if they know Arabic and they are able to adapt these tools, it's really underexplored. So, I definitely push students in that direction if they're interested in learning those methods.

LA: I completely endorse this. One of the things that all of us, collectively, need to be thinking more about is how all of our fields and research agendas are going to be reshaped by artificial intelligence and what you can do with it. That said, while the data itself might be largely unstructured, I don't think any of those AI tools are “unstructured”. They've been structured by somebody else. So, for example, you can scrape web data in Egypt, which is terrific, and I have students who have done that and it's been very instructive, but that means that you are operating at the level of the web. And there are a fair number of people in Egypt who don't live on the web, even now. So, you have to, as a student, say, “Yes, all of this stuff is available, but what is it bringing with it? What are the algorithms doing? What is the uneven availability of this technology doing?” So, as I said, I endorse this idea that we all ought to be exploring this, but I think we shouldn't be behind a veil of ignorance here. There are built-in characteristics to these sorts of data and analytic tools that we need to acknowledge, and perhaps utilize to our benefit. Pretending those structures are not there can lead to reproducing some of the biases that are built in, rather than acknowledging and using them.

DG: Thank you, Salma and Lisa. Are there any other threads we want to tie up before concluding?

JM: May I add one point, actually? I mean, we are living in a crisis, us, those who are here in the region, and producing knowledge and doing research on your own predicament and struggles is often very challenging. At times, this even becomes absurd. I have witnessed this firsthand with the economic and financial collapse in Lebanon. I mean, what would I study? I would only study my very own misery. So, this is something that we all

have to be aware of, let alone the wars and extreme violence that others are experiencing.

The pressure on us to publish, is in itself an ethical question worth raising. Those of us who live in the region place expectations on ourselves (not to make ourselves victims, far from it), but... again, it remains profoundly difficult to study your own misery. Yet, sometimes it looks extremely superficial for others to come and study your own misery, and you become the subject of their research instead of the one who should produce knowledge that is indigenous, in terms of emotions, in terms of tools, techniques, and methods. So this is something to consider. A general comment.

DG: Absolutely. I think that's a really constructive point for all of us to keep in mind. As someone who has done work on Palestine now, it feels almost unethical, or at least ethically complex, to do any research from here that is about people experiencing a genocide while we watch. And, as you've alluded to, some voices from Palestine have been present in popular analysis and news media and such, but in research, you know, are we going to have those voices? How much research will we have in our field, going forward, that's being produced by Palestinians and by Palestinian survivors or those with close connections to survivors?

JM: So there is a gap now between those who can produce and those who cannot.

DG: Right. I want to thank you all again for generously dedicating your time and intellect to this very fruitful discussion.

MENA POLITICS

Newsletter of the Middle East and North Africa Politics Section of APSA

VOL. 8 ISSUE 2, FALL 2025

ISSN: 2996-4911

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The Middle East and North Africa Politics Section is an academic society at the American Political Science Association (APSA), established in 2018 to support, develop and publish research on the politics of the MENA region utilizing interdisciplinary methodological, theoretical and empirical tools. It seeks to fully integrate the rigorous study of the politics of the Middle East with the broader discipline of Political Science, to serve as an institutional home for the community of political scientists dedicated to the Middle East, and to incorporate both scholars from the MENA region and diverse scholars from the United States into the global study of Middle East politics. The section's bylaws and diversity statement can be found on its website, <https://apsamena.org>.

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